

ENTREPRENEDEU

Enhancing entrepreneurial ecosystems for education

D7.2 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION PLAN - FINAL RELEASE

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D7.2 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION PLAN - FINAL RELEASE

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The ENTREPRENEDU project is focused on closing the innovation and educational gap between European Union countries that have unbalanced business activities and fewer job opportunities, due to less developed entrepreneurial ecosystems.

The report D7.2 Dissemination and Communication Plan - final release is the second part of the Dissemination and Communication Plan, highlighted in D7.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan. It provides information on dissemination and communication activities carried out by the ENTREPRENEDU project until January 2024 and its results.

The Dissemination and Communication strategy was divided into three distinct phases with well-defined objectives, being the project currently in the final phase aiming at increasing awareness within the project community, including project stakeholders, and providing visibility to main project's outputs. With six months left until the closure of the project, the majority of the Dissemination and Communication KPIs were already achieved, without any deviation foreseen in this chapter.

Channels used as part of the communication and dissemination actions included social media platforms (such as [LinkedIn](#), [Facebook](#), [Instagram](#), [X](#), and [YouTube](#)), [website](#), and [F6S platform](#). **This multichannel approach was essential to reach out the target audience and achieve the project goals.**

As a result of the dissemination and communication activities a total of 5 videos, 24 blog articles, 26 external media outputs, 8 press releases, 11 newsletters, 8 participation in events, among others, were developed.

LinkedIn became the go to social media platform with the biggest project community being present there (438 followers). Moreover, it also serves as a storytelling proxy since the project's trajectory since inception can be followed and consulted here.

As part of the special promotion campaign of the Hackathons, HackTheBusiness concept and brand was created to better identify and express the project's scope and objective: close the innovation and educational gap by helping young entrepreneurial minds "hack" (i.e. demystify) the business. **More than 1 million potential applicants were reached out by these campaigns, helping Italian, Greek and Bulgarian editions to succeed in their goals.**

[EDU's promotional video](#) premiered during the HackTheBusiness Italy and he was later introduced to the ENTREPRENEDU digital community during his Eurotrip, a different and funny way to get to know our partners.

This report highlights the actions and results from the Dissemination and Communication activities undertaken during the first 24 months. There are still six more left to do more and reach the KPIs, while providing relevant and essential information to our community in a fun and attractive way.

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1 INTRODUCTION

The report **D7.2 Dissemination & Communication Plan - final release** is the second report of WP7 - Dissemination and Communication of the ENTREPRENEDU project. It corresponds to the updated version of the D7.1 Dissemination & Communication Plan.

While the first report leans over the main plan and defined strategy, featuring target audience profiles, branding concept and scope, visuals, among others, the updated version focuses on the results of the dissemination and communication activities implemented by the ENTREPRENEDU consortium.

The dissemination and communication strategy for the ENTREPRENEDU project is divided into three phases, being the last one currently in place with the aim to maximize awareness of project activities. This will result in a higher number of the ENTREPRENEDU community members being reached out. As the project walks towards its closing phase, any featured strategy will represent a big contribution to the exploitation activities, managed within WP6 - Venture Building Program refinement and mutual learning.

Note that the report covers 24 months (out of 30) of the project lifetime, meaning that final results from the dissemination and communication activities will only be known upon the closure of the project. Nevertheless, the preliminary assessment provides excellent guidance on KPIs achievement and potential deviations, which will indicate whether the implementation of corrective actions is necessary or not and the overall success of the project's Dissemination & Communication Strategy

The following chapters are covered in the report:

- **Chapter 1. Introduction** presents a brief description of the report's scope and goal.
- **Chapter 2. Communication and Dissemination Plan** provides an overview of the implementation of the communication and dissemination strategies.
- **Chapter 3. Results** highlights the main results from the communication and dissemination activities.
- **Chapter 4. Conclusion** presents the main takeaways of the report.

2 COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION PLAN (FINAL)

The ENTREPRENEDU communication and dissemination plan described in the **Deliverable 7.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan**, was a strategically planned process with a diverse set of interactive and engaging tools and actions targeting the ENTREPRENEDU main stakeholders and delivering the story of the ENTREPRENEDU journey.

As the project progressed, the communication plan, divided in 3 main complementary phases, centered around empowering young innovators and sharing their stories as well as positioning the ENTREPRENEDU team as their “business companion” and mentor, has proven itself effective over the past 24 months:

- The **first phase [M1-M3]** included the brand development and awareness creation, by following the idea of the young and vibrant entrepreneurial ecosystem ENTREPRENEDU is targeting. The main objective of this phase was to engage stakeholders and enlighten their interest in the project. As a result, the created ENTREPRENEDU brand identity is energetic, professional and modern, highlighted by a vibrant and playful set of colours. In this way, the ENTREPRENEDU project managed to gather a community of young innovators, as well as other stakeholders interested in projects’ objectives and ENTREPRENEDU mission to enhance entrepreneurial education in Europe.
- The **second phase [M4-M18]** included a structured way of informing the target audience about up-to-date insights, while using diverse ENTREPRENEDU online channels (such as [LinkedIn](#), [Facebook](#), [Instagram](#), [X](#), and [YouTube](#)). Meaning that depending on the project activity being in progress, the outcomes were shared in alignment with the target audience mainly affected, across specific channels. Therefore, by following the Inbound marketing strategy as described in D7.1, this phase was executed with a stronger emphasis on a youth-centric approach. This led to a several key decisions made:
 - **Introducing ENTREPREN(EDU):** In M6, a dynamic character representing a young individual embarking on their entrepreneurial journey named EDU served as a relatable figure, guiding youth through the project's key milestones and showcasing the diverse opportunities available within the ENTREPRENEDU ecosystem. EDU was introduced in the form of an animated project explainer-video, showcasing project’s mission in an interactive mode.
 - **Youth-oriented tone of voice:** ENTREPRENEDU communication materials, including website content, social media posts and newsletters adopted a conversational and engaging tone. The idea was to communicate updates in clear, but friendly language, fostering audience participation and a sense of community among young innovators.

- **Interactive content:** Interactive elements were incorporated into the communication strategy, such as engaging memes on the website, promotional materials and interactive polls on social media. These elements encouraged engagement of the younger audience and positioning ENTREPRENEDU activities as an opportunity of their interest.
- Currently, in M24, the project is in the **third phase [M19-M30]**, and final stage of the strategic plan implementation, which means maximising awareness of the key stakeholders on ENTREPRENEDU impact and demonstrating more advanced results of the project. In this phase, the key focus is shifting to stakeholders such as Academia, Industry, Investors and Policy Makers. For example, while a series of 3 ENTREPRENEDU hackathons were disseminated via Instagram Stories ([HackTheBusiness Italy](#), [HackTheBusiness Greece](#) and [HackTheBusiness Bulgaria](#)) as an additional way to engage youth in phase two, ENTREPRENEDU scientific publications were disseminated via the ENTREPRENEDU [website](#), [LinkedIn](#) and [Zenodo](#) account, as more informative and professional channels.

In this same period, by referring to the [Making the Most of Your H2020 Project](#) from the [European IPR Helpdesk](#) booklet which is the basic concept behind projects' theoretical approach, the dissemination plan is being implemented simultaneously, as described in the Deliverable 7.1. Therefore, ENTREPRENEDU results are being publicly available as developed, to those who could benefit from them, such as university professors, industry, policy makers, investors, public authorities or civil society.

Up to M24, the main deviation from the initial version of the ENTREPRENEDU communication and dissemination plan, related to the implementation of the predicted tools and channels, as well as monitoring, is identified as follows:

- Social media: The rebranding of Twitter to X in late 2023 presented a challenge in the performance of the ENTREPRENEDU [Twitter](#) account, accompanied by significant platform instability, including frequent outages, algorithm changes, and a decline in user experience. This instability disrupted the flow of information and made it difficult to maintain a consistent presence on the platform.

The Twitter to X transition highlighted the importance of the communication and dissemination strategy from the initial ENTREPRENEDU communication and dissemination plan described in the Deliverable 7.1, such as platform diversification. Since the beginning, ENTREPRENEDU has been present on five social media platforms, including X. Diversifying communication channels was a crucial decision which ensured adaptability of the projects' social media presence. Recognising the continued strength of LinkedIn as a platform for reaching young professionals, the team shifted its focus to this platform, prioritising content creation and community engagement on LinkedIn. Moreover, regular evaluation of the X platform performance and audience engagement was continuously implemented to follow any changes in performances. So far, no progress has been noted.

3 RESULTS

By referring back to the Grant Agreement, in **Table 6** of the D7.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan, we have represented the communication and dissemination Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). To measure these KPIs, diverse evaluation and tracking systems were used, such as Google Analytics, social media metrics, and an internal dashboard created for this purpose. Table 1 serves as an extension to the table previously mentioned, with periodic time stamps and progress.

TABLE 1. ENTREPRENEDEDU KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS - M24 OVERVIEW

CHANNEL	KPI TRESHOLD	M24	% OF EXECUTION
WEBSITE	Website in M2	Website in M2	100.00%
	>1000 unique visitors	>5900 unique visitors	589.41%
	>20 references in other websites	23 references in other websites	114.99%
SOCIAL MEDIA	>200 followers on each social media page	>630 followers on five social media pages	62.94%
	>80 tweets	>170 tweets	209.87%
	>500 views per post	>3480 views per post	694.61%
VIDEOS	3 promotional videos	7 promotional videos	233.33%
JOURNAL/MAGAZINE ARTICLES, NEWSLETTERS, PRESS RELEASES	>6 journal articles	5 journal articles	83.33%
	>3 magazines news	26 magazines news	650.00%
	>4 newsletters per year	11 newsletters in total	275.00%
	>6 scientific papers released	5 scientific papers released	71.43%
INTERNATIONAL/NATIONAL CONFERENCES, SEMINARS, WORKSHOPS AND MEETINGS WITH CLUSTERS AND ASSOCIATIONS	>4 project outreach events	4 project outreach events	80.00%
	>4 total project presentations	4 total project presentations	80.00%
	>50 participants	>50 participants	100.00%
	3 social media campaigns	4 social media campaigns	133.33%
EVENTS IN THE REFERENCE SECTOR FOCUSING ON BOTH PROFESSIONAL AND GENERAL PUBLIC	> 4 events	4 events	80.00%
	>3 MoU signed*		

	>3 signed collaboration partnerships*		
CLUSTERING WITH OTHER NATIONAL AND EU INITIATIVES	2-3 connections created*	-	-
POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS	> 8 supporting letters* > 2 recommendations* > 1 best practice inventory* > 3 guidelines on standard operating procedures*	-	-

**These activities are not being monitored and tracked within the scope of this report since they will be covered as part of activities from WP6 - Venture Building Program refinement and mutual learning.*

To measure the key indicators, the following evaluation elements were used:

- **Google Analytics** to track and report on the project website traffic.
- **Social Media metrics** to track engagement on ENTREPRENEDU's social networks.
- **Partners Dashboard** as an internal "live" document to track communication and dissemination activities, with contributions from all Consortium Partners.

The monitoring and evaluation framework outlined in D7.1 has effectively guided the analysis of ENTREPRENEDU's dissemination activities. This framework, based on predefined metrics for each platform, has enabled the regular evaluation, measurement, and improvement of dissemination efforts throughout the project.

Overall, by finding a right balance between youth engagement and tailoring the ENTREPRENEDU branding and messaging accordingly to different target audiences (youth, academia, investor, industry, policy makers), the project's main milestones are being successfully published across diverse communication and dissemination channels. However, there are 6 months left of the project, where we expect other KPIs to grow, as well.

A more detailed explanation of the current status of each communication and dissemination tool and channel used for implementing the strategy provided in the initial plan, will be provided in the next subsections of this document.

3.1 SOCIAL MEDIA

As stated in the Deliverable 7.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan, ENTREPRENEDU project is present on five social media channels including LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter (X),

Instagram and YouTube, and has been active in producing and posting interactive content, tailored to the needs of its target audience. In total, the ENTREPRENEDU social media channels have to this date [M25] **639 followers**. This result can be seen in the metrics tracked for the each specific channel, as represented below:

- [LinkedIn](#) - 438 followers

FIGURE 1: ENTREPRENEDU LINKEDIN PAGE

- [Facebook](#) - 36 likes and 45 followers

FIGURE 2: ENTREPRENEDU FACEBOOK PAGE

- [Twitter \(X\)](#) - 176 posts (tweets) and 30 followers

FIGURE 3: ENTREPRENEDU TWITTER (X) PAGE

- [Instagram](#) - 110 followers and 89 posts

FIGURE 4: ENTREPRENEDU INSTAGRAM PAGE

- [YouTube](#) - 16 subscribers and 597 views

FIGURE 5: ENTREPRENEDU YouTube PAGE

With the highest number of followers and the most engaged community, [LinkedIn](#) has turned out to be the key ENTREPRENEDU social media platform. Since the creation of the account in February 2023 [M2], this profile alone has collected more than **148,000 impressions**, both total and sponsored. In the last 365 days, the audience following the ENTREPRENEDU LinkedIn engaged 932 times with the content through liking, sharing and commenting on the posts. Up to this date, the **total number of post engagements is 2,584**.

Figure 6: ENTREPRENEDU LINKEDIN HIGHLIGHTS FOR THE LAST 365 DAYS

Other ENTREPRENEDU media platforms, such as Facebook, Instagram, YouTube and occasionally Twitter (X), are used as dissemination channels for specific targeted groups, depending on the results being disseminated (for more information, consult D7.1).

Up to this date:

- [Facebook](#) reach is **20,200** with more than **1,700 visits**.

FIGURE 7: ENTREPRENEDU FACEBOOK PAGE - REACH AND VISITS

- [Instagram](#) counts **609 profile visits** and **444 link clicks** with more than 50% of the audience being **women**, mostly ages 25-44.

FIGURE 8: ENTREPRENEDU INSTAGRAM PAGE - DEMOGRAPHICS

- Twitter performance started to stagnate after July 2023 and tracking data was possible only via a paid account, due to its transition to X, as explained in the previous section of this document.

- [YouTube](#) gathered **1000 impressions** which led to **1.23 hours of watch time**.

FIGURE 9: ENTREPRENEDU YOUTUBE PAGE - IMPRESSIONS AND WATCH TIME

3.1.1 SOCIAL MEDIA CAMPAIGNS

To enhance awareness, drive traffic, and engage stakeholders, the ENTREPRENEDU communication plan incorporated various campaigns. Some campaigns were already implemented, while others are being deployed or will be deployed in the future, depending on the project's evolving status.

Each social media campaign has a specific goal (sometimes more than one) which are:

- To **inform** and provide up-to-date insights about the project.
- To **educate** target audiences by sharing helpful content.
- To **engage** with key stakeholders by pinpointing relevant topics.
- To **activate** the target audience by expressing a clear call to action.

To provide concrete examples, a number of social media campaigns have been showcased in the table below, while all published posts are available in the [Appendix A: Social media activity](#).

TABLE 2: EXAMPLES OF SOCIAL MEDIA CAMPAIGNS

CAMPAIGN	LINK TOWARDS EXAMPLES (LinkedIn)	GOAL
KICK-OFF	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7029740934061805570	INFORM
AWARENESS	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7034095784987881473 https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7034485760628031488	INFORM ENGAGE
ECOSYSTEM NEWS	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7030851578915880960 https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7049757276877803520	LEARN
WEBSITE	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7038493143045951488	ACTION ENGAGE
NEWSLETTER	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7052222377887174656 https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7148598975875465216	ENGAGE ACTION
PRESS RELEASE	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7031192573255819264	INFORM ENGAGE
GENDER EQUALITY	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7039157810311409664	ENGAGE
EVENTS	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7255238226137825280	INFORM
MENTORING & COACHING INTERVIEWS	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7206942085482975232	INFORM ACTION
VENTURE BUILDING PROGRAMME	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7259852022902833153	INFORM ACTION

SPECIFIC OCCASIONS	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7285219222119481345	ENGAGE
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3.1.2 SPECIAL SOCIAL MEDIA CAMPAIGNS

Together with regular, ENTREPRENEDU activities were presented via special social media campaigns (full list of materials are available at [ENTREPRENEDU's Zenodo Open Repository](#)). Three of four campaigns were oriented towards promoting and disseminating ENTREPRENEDU hackathons:

- **HackTheBusiness Italy** during April-June 2023

ENTREPRENEDU
Enhancing entrepreneurial ecosystems for education

HackTheBusiness | ITALY
HACKATHON
15-17 June, Rimini Expo Centre, Rimini

Let the hacking begin!
Apply at f6s.com/entrepreneur-edu-hackthebusinessitaly/apply

HackTheBusiness | ITALY
DeepTech HACKATHON
15-17 June, Rimini Expo Centre, Rimini

brought to you by:
ENTREPRENEDU

SPACE

FOOD

CLIMATE

Let the hacking begin!

FIGURE 10: BANNER EXAMPLES FOR HACKTHEBUSINESS ITALY SPECIAL SOCIAL MEDIA CAMPAIGN

- **HackTheBusiness Greece** during September-December 2023

**We are looking for innovative
SPACE ideas. Have one?**
Apply today at entrepredu.eu

DU logo" data-bbox="592 218 768 268"/>

Enhancing entrepreneurial ecosystems for education

HackTheBusiness GREECE
is an entrepreneurial
competition for young minds
interested in exploring the
secrets of SPACE!
Join us!

HackTheBusiness GREECE

**If you are between 18 and 40
years old, based in Europe, with
a passion for SPACE -
we are waiting for you!**

Apply today at entrepredu.eu

FIGURE 11: BANNER EXAMPLES FOR HACKTHEBUSINESS GREECE SPECIAL SOCIAL MEDIA CAMPAIGN

- **HackTheBusiness Bulgaria** during February-April 2024

FIGURE 12: BANNER EXAMPLES FOR HACKTHEBUSINESS BULGARIA SPECIAL SOCIAL MEDIA CAMPAIGN

The decision to name this series of hackathons **HackTheBusiness** came from a desire to create a unified and impactful brand identity around these campaigns. This rebranding process involved a collaborative effort within the ENTREPRENEDU consortium. Ultimately,

HackTheBusiness emerged as the preferred choice, reflecting the core values of the hackathon series and target audience (Youth), while maintaining a concise and catchy name.

To maximise participation and engagement in the three HackTheBusiness hackathons, a multi-channel communication strategy was implemented. A comprehensive campaign divided into pre-event, during-event, and post-event phase, included not only strong social media presence on all channels, but also promotion via [blog articles](#), [webinars](#), [warm-up sessions](#), [success stories](#), [case studies](#), [press releases](#), [special newsletters](#), [recap videos](#) and specific “HackTheBusiness” [website pages](#) designed for each event. However, social media played a pivotal role, with dedicated paid campaigns leveraging targeted advertising and engaging content to reach potential participants.

TABLE 3: MAIN ACTIVITIES PERFORMED FOR SPECIAL SOCIAL MEDIA CAMPAIGNS

PHASE	ACTIVITY	HTB Italy	HTB Greece	HTB Bulgaria
Pre-event	Social Media Kit	✓	✓	✓
	Social Media Tizzers	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7046797895609593857	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7105151352422432769	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7161275810446753792
	Paid social media campaign with special social media static and dynamic visuals	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/entrepredu_hackathon-for-individuals-and-startups-activity-7061971483174002688-QfJ0?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/entrepredu_hackthebusiness-in-greece-activity-7120701512913182720-Wz2T?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/entrepredu_join-us-in-bulgaria-activity-7171405656032198657-2RAr?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
	Final countdown	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7071473865943654401	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7072208453498249216	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7177952581732728832
	Special edition of Newsletter	https://mailchi.mp/89a6715aa249/hackthebusinessitaly	https://mailchi.mp/1f76cf3ff39/entrepredu-newletter	https://mailchi.mp/0a93fab8b00/hackthebusinessinbulgaria
	Newsletter Blurb	NA	✓	✓
	Blog article	https://entrepredu.eu/hackthebusiness_italy_hackathon/	https://entrepredu.eu/cheers-to-the-successful-start-of-the-hackthebusiness-competition-in-greece/	https://entrepredu.eu/lets-hackthebusiness-in-bulgaria-for-a-sustainable-future/

	Dedicated Webpage	https://entreprenedu.eu/entreprenedu-hackthebusiness-italy/	https://entreprenedu.eu/hackthebusinessgreece/	https://entreprenedu.eu/hackthebusinessbulgaria/
	Press Release	https://entreprenedu.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/HackTheBusiness-Press-Release.pdf	https://entreprenedu.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/09/Press-releases_ENTREPRENEDU-project-launches-second-HackTheBusiness-competition-in-Greece.pdf	https://entreprenedu.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/02/HackTheBusiness-Bulgaria_PR_ENTREPRENEDU-project-invites-young-professionals-to-shape-a-sustainable-future-in-Bulgaria-.pdf
	Webinar/Warm-up session	https://youtu.be/DdV6QQCUbws	https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLagZS0fUi7cosaFMPaPHqXY7GkSMCCVU	https://entreprenedu.eu/hackthebusinessbulgaria/
During-event	Live event coverage via Instagram story	✓	✓	✓
	Interviews with participants/organisers	✓	✓	✓
	Social media event coverage	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7075520406115229696	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7126201579220664323	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:717834927209907201
Post-event	Meet the Winners	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7077555837786808320	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7135272516876460034	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7180570338211045376
	Blog article	https://entreprenedu.eu/exciting-news-we-are-unveiling-winners-of-the-first-hackthebusiness-competition-held-in-rimini	https://entreprenedu.eu/they-hacked-the-business-in-greece-meet-the-winners/	https://entreprenedu.eu/meet-the-winners-of-the-final-hackthebusiness-contest-held-in-bulgaria/
	Press release	https://entreprenedu.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/07/ENTREPRENEDU-Press-Release--Groundbreaking-ENTREPRENEDU-Press-Release-3-Groundbreaking-ideas-shine-at-ENTREPRENEDUs-first-HackTheBusiness-competition-in-Rimini.pdf	https://entreprenedu.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/11/ENTREPRENEDU-Press-Release-HackTheBusiness-hackathon-brings-together-space-entrepreneurs-for-a-day-in-Greece.pdf	https://entreprenedu.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/04/HackTheBusiness-Bulgaria_PR2_ENTREPRENEDU-project-gathered-sustainable-innovators-in-Sofia-Bulgaria.pdf

	Video	https://youtu.be/9pTOLoLoYrM	https://youtu.be/uviXzi_RTw	https://youtu.be/Gx8pbUu8SJs
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As youth being our primary target audience during HackTheBusiness events, a special attention was dedicated to serving their personal and professional traits. Youth represents young professionals (18-30 years old) – high schoolers and university students interested in entrepreneurship, as well as young startup owners or future entrepreneurs who are dreaming of becoming an owner of a unicorn company in Europe. By developing a 3 series (different for each HackTheBusiness event as presented in figures 13, 14 and 15) of unique and funny meme-stickers, we adopted our approach specifically to them. The goal of this communication style was to make their HackTheBusiness experience correlated with positivity and sense of humor, not only strict professionalism. Our goal was for them to know that we are reachable, as their supporters and mentors.

Moreover, a new set of ENTREPRENEDU promotional materials was developed for each HackTheBusiness special social media campaign, such as tote bags, notebook designs, badges, and pen designs, depending on the request of the main hackathon organisers.

FIGURE 13: HACKTHEBUSINESS ITALY PROMOTIONAL MATERIALS - STICKERS

FIGURE 14: HACKTHEBUSINESS GREECE PROMOTIONAL MATERIALS - STICKERS

FIGURE 15: HACKTHEBUSINESS BULGARIA PROMOTIONAL MATERIALS - STICKERS

FIGURE 16: HACKTHEBUSINESS SPECIAL SOCIAL MEDIA CAMPAIGN - EXAMPLES OF OTHER PROMOTIONAL MATERIALS

This engaging approach proved successful in raising awareness, attracting the right participants, and fostering a vibrant, yet competitive atmosphere throughout the hackathon series. The table below presents overall social media campaign results.

TABLE 4: MAIN KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS RESULTS FROM SPECIAL SOCIAL MEDIA CAMPAIGN

KPIs	HTB Italy #1	HTB Greece #2	HTB Bulgaria #3	Total
Potential Applicants reached (total appox)	>134k	>1 million	>122k	>1.25 million
Potential Applicants reached - Social Media only (total appox)	>27k	>638k	>30k	>695k
No of visitors website	>580	>2000	>1200	>3780
No of visitors webpage	>450	>1700	>830	>2980

In addition to the previously mentioned campaigns, EDU’s Eurotrip campaign was organised during summer 2023, as an interactive and “out of the box” way to introduce the ENTREPRENEDU team to our target audience, rendering it more personal and friendly. With that idea in mind, from Italy to Ireland, EDU traveled to all Consortium members’ countries. This special campaign was published specifically on social media channels and promoted via newsletters.

FIGURE 17: BANNER EXAMPLES FOR EDU'S EUROTRIP SPECIAL SOCIAL MEDIA CAMPAIGN

3.2 WEBSITE

The initial version of the ENTREPRENEDU website (www.entreprenedu.eu) was developed in M2. The website was regularly updated as the project was entering diverse phases of the implementation. Therefore, the initial version of the ENTREPRENEDU website has been upgraded with additional pages and sections, to the present:

- The [Home page](#) was regularly updated with additional information, such as HackTheBusiness call to action or an explainer video.
- The [Journey page](#) remained showcasing different phases of the ENTREPRENEDU project.
- The Insight page initially had three subpages: Blog, Press Kit, Communication Kit. In the third phase of the communication plan, the page was reorganised and currently includes a new subpage, named [Resources](#). The purpose of this new section is to showcase all ENTREPRENEDU major outcomes in open-access, divided by work packages.
- The HackTheBusiness page contains the following subpages: [HackTheBusiness Italy](#), [HackTheBusiness Greece](#) and [HackTheBusiness Bulgaria](#). These pages have been specifically developed to present the main information and registration point for three ENTREPRENEDU hackathons. All pages were updated after hackathons for dissemination purposes.
- The [Blog page](#) was initially part of the Insights. However, in the same period, this page was reorganised to be independent, showcasing all project's main updates.
- The [Contact page](#) still represents the helpdesk point for all interested parties.

Alongside these changes, the website remained the main leading point to all projects' updates and main outcomes.

To emphasise the visibility of the **Funded by the European Union** emblem, the website header was updated in July 2024 [M18]. The header is now fixed with an emblem always visible to the visitors. Additionally, the photo in the hero banner was updated with an emblem positioned in the upper right corner. As before, the emblem is still visible in the footer of the website.

FIGURE 18: ENTREPRENEDU WEBSITE UPDATES - EU FUNDED EMBLEM

Up to M24, the ENTREPRENEDU website was visited by approximately **5,910 active users**, with the average session duration being **2 min and 10 seconds**.

FIGURE 19: ENTREPRENEDU WEBSITE DATA - TOTAL USERS OVER TIME

Interestingly, Figure 19 expresses three picks between April 2023 and April 2024, corresponding to the special social media campaigns organised for the promotion of the three HackTheBusiness events, as previously explained. In total, the number of **page visits** is **12,742**. Specifically, HackTheBusiness Italy with 1,126 visits, HackTheBusiness Greece with 3,066 visits and HackTheBusiness Bulgaria with 1,440 visits. These high numbers confirmed that special social media campaigns were effective in raising attractiveness around events and raising awareness around ENTREPRENEDU in general.

FIGURE 20: ENTREPRENEDU WEBSITE DATA - VIEWS OVER TIME

Looking at the traffic to the project website throughout the first 24 months of the project is also important for understanding if communication efforts are performing. Figure XY explains that the majority of users are visiting the ENTREPRENEDU website directly (Direct traffic), or through call to actions via social media channels or newsletters (Organic traffic). More specifically, the **number of total sessions is 8,190** with **40,04% engagement rate**.

FIGURE 21: ENTREPRENEDU WEBSITE DATA - SESSIONS OVER TIME

Finally, website users are mostly coming from Italy (~ 380), Bulgaria (~ 650), Greece (~ 790), together with the United Kingdom and Germany (~ 1300).

3.3 F6S PLATFORM

Another important channel used by the ENTREPRENEDU consortium was the [F6S platform](#) (Figure 22). Here, the project managed registration processes for the three Hackathons (Figure 23), as well as related events, such as webinars (Figure 24).

FIGURE 22: ENTREPRENEDU PAGE ON F6S PLATFORM. SOURCE: [HTTPS://WWW.F6S.COM/ENTREPRENEDU-PROJECT/ABOUT](https://www.f6s.com/entreprenedu-project/about). VISITED ON 23/01/2025

FIGURE 23: HACKTHEBUSINESS BULGARIA REGISTRATION PAGE. SOURCE: [HTTPS://WWW.F6S.COM/ENTREPRENEDU-HACKTHEBUSINESSBULGARIA](https://www.f6s.com/entreprenedu-hackthebusinessbulgaria). VISITED ON 23/01/2025

FIGURE 24: HACKTHEBUSINESS ITALY - WEBINAR REGISTRATION PAGE. SOURCE: [HTTPS://WWW.F6S.COM/HACKTHEBUSINESS-ITALY-WEBINAR](https://www.f6s.com/hackthebusiness-italy-webinar). VISITED ON 23/01/2025

The complementarity with the website allowed an effective management of applicants' registrations, while it has also served as an important vehicle for promoting activities. By being displayed and linked to the ENTREPRENEDU project, selected projects/teams have seen their visibility and credibility grow within the community by being associated with a programme supported and funded by the European Commission.

Moreover, the platform was also used as the main communication channel between mentors and mentees during the implementation of the three editions of the Mentoring & Coaching Programme.

3.4 VIDEOS

An [ENTREPRENEDU YouTube channel](#) was created at the beginning of the project with the goal of it being a video repository and host content ranging from promotional videos to online events and recaps. YouTube served as a valuable platform for disseminating project information. We utilized the channel to create engaging recap videos of special social media campaigns and informative videos introducing the ENTREPRENEDU project.

As already mentioned and showcased in the picture below, the channel currently counts **597 views**, has **17 subscribers** and **1000 impressions** with **11.3h of watch time**. Moreover, the

channel has [1 playlist containing 3 different recordings](#), all related to the special social media campaign - HackTheBusiness Bulgaria. The playlist counts a total of **61 views**.

FIGURE 25: ENTREPRENEDU YouTube - LIFETIME ANALYTICS

According to the YouTube analytics, top 3 video performers are:

- [ENTREPRENEDU Project: Get to know us better!](#) - an official project explainer video with 214 views and 0:50 average view duration,
- [ENTREPRENEDU | #HackTheBusiness Bulgaria Webinar](#) - webinar recording with 99 views and 1:57 average view duration, and
- [ENTREPRENEDU | HackTheBusiness Greece](#) - a hackathon recap video with 92 views and 0:32 average view duration.

Having in mind that there are 6 months left until the end of the initiative, a recap video will be created, emphasizing main project highlights and the impact ENTREPRENEDU has established during its life cycle.

3.5 BLOG ARTICLES

The ENTREPRENEDU project has significantly exceeded its initial blogging goals. While the D7.1 document outlined a plan for a minimum of 3 blog articles targeting relevant stakeholders, the project has successfully created and published 24 blog posts on the [ENTREPRENEDU website's Blog page](#).

Collectively, these blog posts have garnered **over 700 views**, demonstrating their effectiveness in reaching and engaging the target audience. Such articles serve various purposes, including informative, inspirational, and promotional content:

- **Informative:**
 - [Exciting news: ENTREPRENEDU project kicks off in Rome](#)
 - [We were in Baku, Azerbaijan to present the first ENTREPRENEDU scientific paper](#)
 - [A Recap of the first ENTREPRENEDU General Assembly Meeting in Rimini](#)
 - [The official start of the ENTREPRENEDU Mentoring & Coaching Programme](#)
 - [Enhancing entrepreneurial education: The start of the ENTREPRENEDU Venture Building Programme](#)
- **Interviews:**
 - [ENTREPRENEDU Mentoring & Coaching Programme: Insights from Fraunhofer IPK](#)
 - [ENTREPRENEDU Mentoring & Coaching Programme: Insights from E. Amaldi Foundation](#)
 - [ENTREPRENEDU Mentoring & Coaching Programme: Insights from Luiss Guido Carli University](#)
 - [ENTREPRENEDU Mentoring & Coaching Programme: Insights from European Business Angel Network](#)
 - [ENTREPRENEDU Mentoring & Coaching Programme: Insights from Corallia](#)
 - [ENTREPRENEDU Mentoring & Coaching Programme: Insights from CleanTech Bulgaria](#)
- **Inspirational:**
 - [ENTREPRENEDU Mentoring & Coaching Programme: End marks new beginnings](#)
 - [The Role of Mentorship in Competitions: Why Having a Mentor Can Make All the Difference](#)
- **Part of the special social media campaign:**
 - [HackTheBusiness – Unleashing the power of innovation for Young professionals and Startups](#)
 - [Join the HackTheBusiness Webinar and learn about this not-to-miss event in Italy](#)
 - [Exciting news: We are Unveiling Winners of the first HackTheBusiness Competition held in Rimini](#)
 - [How to Build a Winning Team at the HackTheBusiness contest: Strategies for Success](#)
 - [The Top Emerging Technology Trends to Watch in the Space Sector](#)
 - [Unleash Your Entrepreneurial Potential: The Benefits of Attending a HackTheBusiness Competition](#)
 - [Cheers to the successful start of the HackTheBusiness competition in Greece](#)
 - [They hacked the business in Greece: Meet the Winners](#)
 - [Let's HackTheBusiness in Bulgaria for a Sustainable Future](#)
 - [It's a wrap: Meet the Winners of the Final HackTheBusiness contest held in Bulgaria](#)

3.6 EXTERNAL MEDIA

By M24, the ENTREPRENEDU project has garnered significant media attention, thanks to a strong collaborative effort from Consortium Partners. This resulted in substantial media coverage, including **23 website references, 26 news articles, and 5 magazine pieces**. This extensive media coverage effectively disseminated project information to a wider audience that included the own contexts of the consortium partners, creating significant impact on a local and regional level, during special social media campaigns, mostly HackTheBusiness Greece, raising awareness of ENTREPRENEDU's HackTheBusiness events.

The list of materials has been already provided as Appendix A. Dissemination and Communication activities, in Technical Report (Part B). However, the newest addition to that list are the following magazine articles:

- [Безплатно онлайн обучение по предприемачество е достъпно с кандидатстване до 5 ноември](#) published by uchi.bg from Bulgaria on November 4, 2024.
- [Безплатно онлайн обучение по предприемачество е достъпно с кандидатстване до 5 ноември](#) published by ENTREPRENEUR.BG from Bulgaria;
- [Безплатно онлайн обучение по предприемачество е достъпно с кандидатстване до 5 ноември](#) published by Project Media from Bulgaria on November 4, 2024.

By the end of the project, our goal as a Consortium will be to continue collaboration with external media in sharing ENTREPRENEDU's key outcomes.

3.7 PRESS RELEASES

From the beginning of the project until M24, there are 8 press releases developed and available on the project website, subpage [Press Kit](#). These press releases provided journalists with timely and valuable information, supplementing their stories and fostering a deeper understanding of the ENTREPRENEDU project while aligning with the external media engagement strategy of the project. To be more specific:

- [ENTREPRENEDU project is enhancing entrepreneurial ecosystems for education](#) was published on January 20, 2023;
- [ENTREPRENEDU launches series of hackathons named HackTheBusiness to support young professionals](#) was published on May 2, 2023;
- [Groundbreaking ideas shine at ENTREPRENEDU's first HackTheBusiness competition in Rimini, Italy](#) was published on July 3, 2023;
- [ENTREPRENEDU project launches second HackTheBusiness competition in Greece](#) was published on September 15, 2023;
- [HackTheBusiness hackathon brings together space entrepreneurs for a day in Greece](#) was published on November 15, 2023;

- [ENTREPRENEDU project invites young professionals to shape a sustainable future in Bulgaria](#) was published on February 28, 2023;
- [ENTREPRENEDU project assembled sustainability innovators in Sofia, Bulgaria for the final HackTheBusiness event](#) was published on March 29, 2024, and
- [ENTREPRENEDU Mentoring & Coaching Programme Celebrates Success](#) was published on October 11, 2024.

By the end of the project, we will create an additional press release focusing on dissemination of the final project outcomes and achievements to a wider audience. This will ensure enhanced visibility, and leave a positive lasting impression, as well as serve as a summary of all work carried out and all that has been achieved, representing a comfortable point of reference for the key happenings of the project.

3.8 NEWSLETTERS

The project disseminated key activities and outcomes through a series of newsletters. Currently the ENTREPRENEDU newsletter has **156 subscribers**. Utilising the Mailchimp platform, a total number of **11 newsletters** (regular and specials linked to special media campaigns) were crafted and distributed. To be more specific:

- [Newsletter #1](#) was sent on April 13, 2023 to 17 recipients, with 81.3% open-rate and 25% click-rate;
- [Newsletter special edition - HackTheBusiness Italy](#) was sent on June 14, 2023 to 28 recipients, with 63% open-rate and 11.1% click-rate;
- [Newsletter #2](#) was sent on July 14, 2023 to 50 recipients, with 56.3% open-rate and 18.8% click-rate;
- [Newsletter #3](#) was sent on September 25, 2023 to 50 recipients, with 57.1% open-rate and 4.1% click-rate;
- [Newsletter special edition - HackTheBusiness Greece](#) was sent on November 16, 2023 to 110 recipients, with 61.1% open-rate and 10.2% click-rate;
- [Newsletter #4](#) was sent on January 12, 2024 to 112 recipients, with 48.6% open-rate and 5.4% click-rate;
- [Newsletter special edition - HackTheBusiness Bulgaria](#) was sent on March 14, 2025 to 112 recipients, with 38.7% open-rate and 0.9% click-rate;
- [Newsletter #5](#) was sent on April 19, 2024 to 149 recipients, with 52.3% open-rate and 5.4% click-rate;
- [Newsletter #6](#) was sent on July 12, 2024 to 156 recipients, with 51.3% open-rate and 2% click-rate;
- [Newsletter #7](#) was sent on October 17, 2024 to 155 recipients, with 51% open-rate and 0.7% click-rate, and
- [Newsletter #8](#) was sent on January 14, 2025 to 158 recipients, with 32% open-rate and 0.7% click-rate.

These newsletters served as a valuable communication tool, keeping stakeholders informed about project progress and achievements in a longer-format as compared to regular social media posts, which allows for a deeper exposition of project news. All newsletters were disseminated via ENTREPRENEDU social media channels.

3.9 PARTICIPATION IN DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION EVENTS

The ENTREPRENEDU project recognizes the critical importance of dissemination and outreach activities. To date, the project has successfully participated in five relevant events, each having more than 50 participants:

- **We Make Future in Rimini (Italy) in June, 2023** as a communication effort and part of HackTheBusiness Italy organisation.
 - [YouTube recap video](#)
- **International Astronautical Congress in Baku (Azerbaijan) in October 2023** as a dissemination activity and project outreach session.
 - [Blog article](#)
- **Spring of Innovation in Turin (Italy) in April, 2024** as a communication effort.
 - [LinkedIn post](#)
- **Webit/Future Forum in Sofia (Bulgaria) in October, 2024** as a communication effort.
 - [LinkedIn post](#)
- **International Astronautical Congress (IAC) in Milan (Italy) in October, 2024** as a dissemination activity and project outreach session.
 - [LinkedIn post](#)

However, understanding the significant benefits of continued engagement, the Consortium Partners are committed to attending additional events in the final stages of the project, including the project's Final Event, which will serve as a closing moment and final occasion for dissemination. This collaborative effort will ensure maximum visibility, impact, and knowledge transfer.

3.10 DISSEMINATION OF RESULTS

To ensure the widespread dissemination and accessibility of project outputs, all public deliverables and approved open-access scientific publications were categorised by their respective work packages and uploaded to the dedicated [Resources page](#) on the ENTREPRENEDU project website.

FIGURE 26: ENTREPRENEDU RESOURCES WEBPAGE - THE STRUCTURE

The webpage structure in the form of an accordion allows for easy navigation and access to a wide range of resources, including reports, presentations, tools, guidelines, publications and similar documents. This approach facilitates the effective sharing of knowledge and best practices with the broader research community and interested stakeholders.

At the moment, the ENTREPRENEDU project has produced 5 scientific publications, all available on the Resource page, under Work Package 7 - Communication and Dissemination:

- Maximising Hackathon Impact: A Comprehensive Framework for Sustaining Post-Event Outcome [DOI: <https://doi.org/10.34190/ecie.19.1.2798>];
- Enhancing the European entrepreneurial ecosystem by closing the gap between high and low/moderate innovation regions: the ENTREPRENEDU case [DOI: <https://doi.org/10.34190/ecie.19.1.2798>];
- The ENTREPRENEDU Programme: An Educational and scalable model for enhancing the European Entrepreneurial Ecosystems [DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14237207>]
- Empowering Future Entrepreneurs: Developing an Online Entrepreneurial Mentoring Program across diverse EU Regions [DOI: <https://doi.org/10.34190/ecie.19.1.2599>], and
- Tailoring Entrepreneurial Education: Demand-driven Insights for an Entrepreneurial Online Mentoring Program [DOI: <https://doi.org/10.34190/ecel.23.1.2852>]

Furthermore, the ENTREPRENEDU project utilised the **Zenodo platform** for the publication of all scientific publications. The project maintains a [dedicated account on Zenodo](#), where all eligible publications are continuously uploaded and made freely available to the public. This approach aligns with open science principles, maximising the impact and accessibility of research findings and fostering collaboration within the scientific community.

3.11 ADDITIONAL COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

To enhance the overall communication strategy and to strengthen the project's dissemination efforts, a range of supportive materials were developed:

- [Communication kit](#) available in the ENTREPRENEDU website, as a webpage containing all necessary and downloadable information regarding the ENTREPRENEDU brand identity with a goal to unify communication activities, both internally and externally, rendering it unique and immediately recognisable.
- [Press kit](#) as a downloadable document available on the website with a purpose to provide full and immediate support to all media outlets interested in the ENTREPRENEDU project.
- [Standard Project Presentation](#) as an editable presentation available in the main project repository that elaborates ENTREPRENEDUs' methodology and objectives, developed for more effective project dissemination during onsite or online events. The presentation below was used for the HackTheBusiness Italy special social media campaign, more specifically webinar.

FIGURE 27: ENTREPRENEDU STANDARD PROJECT PRESENTATION

- 3 Newsletter blurbs as a type of synergy tool with a short paragraph about key project updates with a complementary visual, ready to be used by Consortium Partners or third parties. Here's an example of the newsletter blurb created for the HackTheBusiness Bulgaria special social media campaign:

ENTREPRENEDU Enhancing entrepreneurial ecosystems for education

NOTE: FEEL FREE TO EDIT THE BLURB ACCORDING TO THE NEEDS OF YOUR RESPECTIVE MARKETING DEPARTMENT.

HACKTHEBUSINESS IN BULGARIA

Name of the Partner and [ENTREPRENEDU project](#) invite you to participate in the final round of the **ENTREPRENEDU HackTheBusiness Bulgaria**, an entrepreneurial hackathon for students, young professionals, and early-stage startups. This transformative event is set to unfold on **March 26th and 27th at the Innovation Forum "John Atanasoff" within Sofia Tech Park**. This year's topic promises to ignite the spark of innovation, shaping the future of sustainable business through eco-conscious solutions. **Registrations are open until 25th of March 2024!** Find more information [here](#).

The poster features a central figure in a lab coat working in a laboratory. Surrounding the figure are labels for various industries: 'digital & creative industries', 'construction', 'agri-food', and 'manufacturing'. The event title 'HackTheBusiness BULGARIA' and dates '26 & 27 March, Sofia' are prominently displayed. A small European Union logo is visible in the bottom right corner of the poster.

 Funded by the European Union

FIGURE 28: ENTREPRENEDU NEWSLETTER BLURB - HTB BULGARIA

4 CONCLUSION

The ENTREPRENEDU project, dedicated to fostering entrepreneurial skills and mindsets among young individuals, has successfully been implementing the initial version of the **Deliverable 7.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan**, through a multi-channel approach. By dividing a comprehensive communication and dissemination strategy in several phases, the project keeps effectively disseminating its findings, engaging stakeholders, and maximising its impact. This strategy, as consistently refined, proved to be instrumental in achieving the majority of identified KPIs, even before the end of the project's lifetime. The rest of the KPIs are expected to be achieved by the end of the project.

The strategy encompassed a diverse range of channels, including the project website, strategically selected social media platforms (with a particular emphasis on LinkedIn), informative newsletters, impactful press releases, and targeted engagement at key industry events. This multifaceted approach not only enhanced project visibility but also fostered meaningful connections with key stakeholders. With 500% more visitors than initially anticipated present at the ENTREPRENEDU website over time, we can confirm that the communication and dissemination strategy is working effectively.

The "HackTheBusiness" hackathon series emerged as a cornerstone of the project's engagement strategy. These dynamic events, promoted in 3 phases through diverse communication and dissemination channels, such as social media, blog articles, press releases, targeted teasers, videos, dedicated website pages, successfully attracted a diverse pool of young innovators and fostered a vibrant entrepreneurial community. All 3 campaigns, together with the introduction of EDU, the main project character, brought ENTREPRENEDU to the spotlight in front of younger audiences, interested in pursuing their innovative ideas and turning them into a reality.

Dedication of the Consortium Partners and a proactive media outreach strategy aligned with the special social media campaigns, brought significant results. A total of eight press releases were strategically disseminated throughout the project's lifecycle, providing journalists with valuable insights and enhancing public understanding of ENTREPRENEDU's achievements. These releases, readily accessible on the project website's dedicated "Press Kit" subpage, served as valuable resources for media professionals, facilitating accurate and comprehensive reporting on project outcomes. On the other hand, a total number of 55 diverse articles were disseminated, some internally via Blog webpage, some externally via third party media outlets.

Throughout the project, a strong emphasis was placed on continuous improvement and adaptation. The communication strategy evolved in response to emerging trends and unforeseen challenges, such as the transition of Twitter to X, which caused the stagnation of ENTREPRENEDU's X account. As a mitigation strategy, the communication team has proactively shifted its effort to LinkedIn which proved itself as the strongest amongst other 2 ENTREPRENEDU social media channels (Facebook and Instagram). This adaptability, coupled

with a data-driven approach to decision-making, ensured that communication efforts remained effective and aligned with project objectives.

Furthermore, in the late stages, the project is prioritizing open access and knowledge sharing. A dedicated Resources page on the project website was developed to provide easy access to a repository of project deliverables, reports, and other valuable project outcomes. Moreover, the project embraced open science principles by utilising the Zenodo platform to publish all scientific publications, ensuring their accessibility and fostering collaboration within the broader research community.

Besides sharing open knowledge, the main goal is to promote the ENTREPRENEDU journey and Venture Building Programme as a scalable and replicable educational model to academia. During the last six months of the project, all Consortium members will collaborate in providing our target audience with the latest project information and practical activities, such as implementation of the Venture Building Programme in different academic facilities ([example](#)). Lastly, until the end of the project the team's effort will be made for achieving all key performance indicators.

Having in mind that the ENTREPRENEDU project is currently in the M25 of 30, final results of the dissemination and communication activities, which are expected to be positive, will be made available in the **Technical Report of the Final Periodic Report** once the project comes to an end.

● APPENDIX A. SOCIAL MEDIA ACTIVITY

Caption	Campaign	Link to post
<p>“Funded by the European Union under the Grant Agreement 101100507. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”</p>	KICK-OFF CAMPAIGN	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7028668932001517568
<p>Hello World! 🙌🌍</p> <p>We are happy to announce the kick-off of the ENTREPRENEDU project! 🎉</p> <p>Interested? Stay tuned for more information!</p>	KICK-OFF CAMPAIGN	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7029023041074384897
<p>Last week, #ENTREPRENEDU team travelled to Italy to held its Kick-off meeting in Italian Space Agency @AgenziaSpacialeItaliana nearby beautiful Rome.</p> <p>The meeting was successfully organized by the Project Coordinator @Fondazione E. Amaldi and assembled diverse innovation stakeholders and educational entities from 6 different European countries - Italy, Bulgaria, Greece, Belgium, Germany and Ireland.</p>	KICK-OFF CAMPAIGN	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7029740934061805570
<p>Take an exclusive #behindthescene look of the ENTREPRENEDU's Kick-off meeting in Rome! 📷</p> <p>Music: Voyage</p>	KICK-OFF CAMPAIGN	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7029797195780378625

<p>Artist: @iksonmusic</p> <p></p>		
<p>Interested in the European Innovation Ecosystems (EIE) Work Programme ? 🙌</p> <p>The EIE Work Programme, as part of the “Innovative Europe” aims to create more connected, inclusive and efficient #innovation ecosystems that support the scaling of companies and spur innovation to address important challenges.</p> <p>Register to this online event and find out more 📌 https://lnkd.in/eRAtTxAj</p> <p></p>	LINK SHARING	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7030851578915880960
<p>Do you have any ideas about what is #ENTREPRENEDU and what are we trying to accomplish? 🗣️</p> <p>👁️ Read our first #pressrelease and let us know if you have any questions in the comments below!</p> <p></p>	INFORMATIVE CAMPAIGN	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7031192573255819264
<p>You are looking at our social media pages, but you are interested in learning more? 🧐</p> <p>Well.. we are here to help! You can always 📧 us at hello@entreprenedu.eu for any of your thoughts about #ENTREPRENEDU project 🙌</p> <p></p>	INFORMATIVE CAMPAIGN	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7032334638412886016
<p>ENTREPRENEDU stands for enhancing entrepreneurial ecosystems for education. 📖</p> <p>Our objective is to support, share knowledge, build confidence, provide advices, as well as best practices to future #entrepreneurs ! 🙌</p> <p>We offer a business #opportunity for high school and university students to build their professional path more easily and potentially create new EU</p>	AWARENESS CAMPAIGN - What?	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7034095784987881473

<p>based #unicorn companies!</p> <p></p>		
<p>We already know that #ENTREPRENEDU project is enhancing entrepreneurial ecosystems for education. 🇪🇺 But, why are we on this mission? 🚀</p> <p>We will tackle two major challenges that #EUInnovationEcosystems are coping with:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 📌 A need for a supporting mechanism for young #entrepreneurs in building up their professional path and potentially create new business #unicorns 🦄 📌 An #innovation asymmetry between different #EU regions which is leading to an innovation gap, missing #knowhow and lack of cooperation 🤝 <p>How? Stay tuned to find out more! 🤔</p> <p></p>	<p>AWARENESS CAMPAIGN - Why?</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7034485760628031488</p>
<p>#ENTREPRENEDU project is an adventure filled with possibilities, important missions and interesting events for future entrepreneurs 🚀 One of those events are 3 ENTREPRENEDU Hackathons that will be organised in Italy, Bulgaria and Greece!</p> <p>We are already preparing the #ENTREPRENEDU Hackathon #1 🙌 Any ideas about the theme?</p> <p></p>	<p>AWARENESS CAMPAIGN - Intro to ENTREPRENED U Hackathons.</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7037011055163666433</p>
<p>What better way to start this #Monday than announcing that #ENTREPRENEDU website is no longer under maintenance? 🙌</p> <p>ENTREPRENEDU website looks young and modern and its ready to enhance entrepreneurial ecosystems for education in a big style! 😎</p> <p>Take a quick look and let us know what do you think in the comments! 🙌</p> <p>https://entprenedu.eu/</p>	<p>WEBSITE CAMPAIGN - We are online!</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7038493143045951488</p>

<p>P.S. What is your #HappyMonday news?</p> <p></p>		
<p>Have you already seen our new stylish-sleek-fun website? 📱</p> <p>Not yet? Go, and check it out at entreprenedu.eu 😎</p> <p>Here's the shortcut 👉 https://entreprenedu.eu/</p> <p></p>	<p>WEBSITE CAMPAIGN - Homepage</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7038922154570080257</p>
<p></p>	<p>IWD</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7039157810311409664</p>
<p>Today, we are (sc)rolling through the #ENTREPRENEDU Journey! 🚗</p> <p>Join us at https://lnkd.in/eO9FSZEp</p> <p></p>	<p>WEBSITE CAMPAIGN - Journey</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7039947069830090752</p>
<p>Jump into the pool of #ENTREPRENEDU Insights where you will find the story about our #brand and the latest #pressreleases and #blogarticles 🏊</p> <p></p>	<p>WEBSITE CAMPAIGN - Insights</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7041703939162927104</p>
<p> Solve the riddle! 🧠</p> <p>What is cool, useful and always up-to-date? 🤔</p>	<p>NEWSLETTER TIZZ</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7042399356947193857</p>

<p>Comment below or click for the answer! 📌</p> <p>🟡🟢🔴</p>		
<p>Are you chasing #hackathons? You are at the right place! 📍</p> <p>ENTREPRENEDU will organise not 1, not 2, but 3 hackathons for students and young professionals who want to pursue their business ideas and level-up their professional carrier! 📌</p> <p>#ENTREPRENEDU will support 12 teams and start-ups selected during #hackathons and provide them with up to 🕒60 hours🕒 of #mentoring through webinars and #coaching workshops!</p> <p>Investigate this #business #opportunity deeper 📌</p> <p>https://entreprenedu.eu/</p> <p>🟡🟢🔴</p>	<p>AWARENESS CAMPAIGN - Intro to Hackathons</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7043913436732219392</p>
<p>Up to 90 students and young professionals will have the opportunity to pitch their business ideas and participate in our Venture Building Program, where they will be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 🟡 Access different modules and supportive documents and materials 🟢 Receive up to 1080 hours of mentoring 🔴 Connect with business accelerators and companies <p>You can be one of them! 😊</p> <p>First #ENTREPRENEDU Hackathon is loading ⌚</p> <p>Find out more at 📌 https://lnkd.in/dGSYTsty</p> <p>🟡🟢🔴</p>	<p>AWARENESS CAMPAIGN - Intro to Venture Building Programme</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7044578531384700928</p>
<p>Talking about opportunities... Don't miss #ENTREPRENEDU Hackathon in Italy! #StayTuned</p>	<p>HACKATHONS TIZZ CAMPAIGN</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:704</p>

		6797895609593857
<p>Stay in the #knowledge loop - join the @ENTREPRENEDU #newsletter 📧 http://eepurl.com/ilqOzy</p>	NEWSLETTER TIZZ	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7047134644508499968
<p>#ThursdayFunFact Hey (future) #entrepreneurs, do you know which country in #Europe is the best one to start a #business in 2023? The answer might surprise you! 🤖 https://lnkd.in/ee27HX4T</p>	LINK SHARING	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7049757276877803520
<p>@ENTREPRENEDU brings together #innovation stakeholders and #educational institutions from different #European countries, connecting low/moderate innovation regions with high innovation ones. Why, you might ask? 🤔 Well, we are here to enhance #competitiveness of the European entrepreneurial ecosystem and close the #innovation and #education gaps between lower and higher performance countries. 🚀 #LetsDoThis 🤝👉</p>	AWARENESS CAMPAIGN	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7051904204591763456
<p>@ENTREPRENEDU #newsletter #1 is out! Inside, you can find main #ENTREPRENEDU insights, a special invitation to our next #event and something extra. Sounds good? Subscribe 📧 http://eepurl.com/ilqOzy</p>	NEWSLETTER OUT	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7052222377887174656
<p>Have you tried this technique yet? 🤔 https://www.nirandfar.com/timeboxing/</p>	LINK SHARING	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7052222377887174656

		3992014480121856
<p>Looking for a #hackathon? 🔍 You are at the right place! 😊</p> <p>More information loading ⌚</p>	HACKATHON	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7054466751329185793
<p>Are you ready to #HackTheBusiness in #Italy? 😊</p> <p>Investigate further 🖱️ https://bit.ly/3V4bhAF</p>	HACKATHON	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7056899742009561088
<p>Let's #HackTheBusiness! 😊</p> <p>📍 June 15-17 Rimini, Italy</p> <p>#HackTheBusiness is an entrepreneurship challenge for young minds to learn, explore and discover the secrets of #DeepTech industry! 🙌</p> <p>This is a “not-to-miss” opportunity for #individuals (18-40 years old) & #startups (up to 1 year old) from #EU who wish to gain business experience, network and level-up while having fun! 🤖</p> <p>Applications are now officially open!</p> <p>🔗 https://bit.ly/3V4bhAF</p> <p>#HackTheBusiness with us! 🚀</p>	HACKATHON	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7058074710881767424
<p>Let's #HackTheBusiness! 😊</p> <p>📍 June 15-17 Rimini, Italy</p>	HACKATHON	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7059051398801371136

<p>Are you an #individual (18-40 years old) or #startup (up to 1 year old) from #EU who wish to gain business experience, network and level-up in business? 🚀 Join the #ENTREPRENEDU fun in Italy!</p> <p>Applications are now officially open! https://bit.ly/3V4bhAF</p> <p>#HackTheBusiness with us! 🚀</p>		
<p>Want to #HackTheBusiness with us in Italy, but not sure how? 😊 We got you! 🙌</p> <p>https://bit.ly/3V4bhAF</p> <p>Let's #HackTheBusiness! 😎 📅 June 15-17 Rimini, Italy</p>	<p>HACKATHON</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7059791270042288128</p>
<p>Today is #EuropeDay 🇪🇺</p> <p>#ENTREPRENEDU is very much proud to be one of the #EU supported projects with a mission to enhance entrepreneurial knowledge of youth across Europe! 🚀</p> <p>P.S. Don't forget to #HackTheBusiness with us! 😎 https://bit.ly/3V4bhAF 📅 June 15-17 Rimini, Italy</p>	<p>EU DAY + HACKATHON</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7061645687658004481</p>
<p>Interested in #DeepTech and #hackathons? We are, too! 🙌</p> <p>So, we are organizing #HackTheBusiness where you can tell us more about your innovative solutions from areas such as #space 🚀 #food 🍴 and #climate 🌍</p>	<p>HACKATHON</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7062360437966671873</p>

<p>If you're #student, a young #entrepreneur, or an one-year-old #startup, this event is a great #opportunity to gain business experience, network with like-minded people and win prizes! 🎁</p> <p>Join us, applications are now open! 📌</p> <p>https://bit.ly/3V4bhAF</p> <p>🟦🟡🟠</p>		
<p>Are you an #individual or a #startup interested in #space #food or #climate technologies? You will love #HackTheBusiness! 🕶️</p> <p>This is an #entrepreneurship opportunity for young minds who have some potentially #cool and innovative ideas to share them with mentors and receive valuable feedback! 🙌</p> <p>📌 Grab your place, applications are open until 9th of June! #HackTheBusiness with us starting from today!</p> <p>https://bit.ly/3V4bhAF</p> <p>🟦🟡🟠</p>	HACKATHON	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7063773693365166080
<p>Interested to read more about #HackTheBusiness #Italy event? We got you covered! 📌 https://lnkd.in/dDGqvSD7</p> <p>Apply today and #HackTheBusiness with us! 🙌</p> <p>https://bit.ly/3V4bhAF</p> <p>🟦🟡🟠</p>	HACKATHON	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7064166430660866048
<p>Want to #HackTheBusiness in #Italy with us? But, you are not sure you have all the answers? 😞 Join our #Webinar to learn more about the event and get your questions answered by the one and only - #ENTREPRENEDEDU organising team! 🕶️</p> <p>📌 MAY 30 5-6 PM CET</p>	HACKATHON	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7064912308497465345

<p>https://bit.ly/3MBMIYZ</p> <p>Apply and be 100% ready to #HackTheBusiness in Italy with us! 🚀</p> <p>● ● ●</p>		
<p>🚀 HackTheBusiness Italy Webinar Meet the #organisingteam of the #HackTheBusiness #Italy hackathon and ask us any questions you might have about the event! 😎</p> <p>🗓️ MAY 30 5-6 PM CET</p> <p>Be 100% ready to #HackTheBusiness in Italy with us! 🚀 Apply today 👉 https://bit.ly/3MBMIYZ</p> <p>All you need to know about the #Webinar is on the link below 📌 👁️ https://lnkd.in/dbzz-9KY</p> <p>● ● ●</p>	HACKATHON	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7066338498932355072</p>
<p>Learn more about this not-to-miss #hackathon organised by the #ENTREPRENEDEU team! 😎📌 https://lnkd.in/dFME4bt4</p> <p>P.S. If you have any question about the #HackTheBusiness event, join us at our Webinar on 30th of May at 5 PM CET - we will be there to answer any doubts! 🙋</p> <p>Here's the Webinar registration link 📌 https://bit.ly/3MBMIYZ</p> <p>Let's #HackTheBusiness in Italy!</p> <p>● ● ●</p>	HACKATHON	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7067435421357490177</p>
<p>Want to join #HackTheBusiness hackathon, but you are not sure do you have what it takes? 😬 We are here to help! Join us tomorrow and chat</p>	HACKATHON	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/</p>

<p>directly with the organising team! 🙌</p> <p>Here's the registration link: https://bit.ly/3MBMIYZ</p> <p>Let's #HackTheBusiness in Italy!</p>		ed/update/urn:li:activity:7068857530277335040
<p>#ENTREPRENEDU #HackTheBusiness #Webinar is live! 📺</p> <p>If you wish to ask any question about #HackTheBusiness event, feel free to join us by clicking on the link below 🙌 https://lnkd.in/djBVJBdp</p> <p>See you soon in Italy! 🚀</p>	<p>HACKATHON</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7069330362207772672
<p>Missed #HackTheBusiness #Webinar? 😞</p> <p>No worries 😊</p> <p>You can rewatch it whenever you have time, as the recording is available at our #youtube channel!</p> <p>Here is the shortcut 🙌 https://lnkd.in/dFRgrNey</p> <p>Let's #HackTheBusiness together! 🙌</p>	<p>HACKATHON - WEBINAR</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7069988174806007808
<p>📅 5 more days to apply 📺</p>	<p>HACKATHON</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:707

<p>#HackTheBusiness in #Italy is an entrepreneurship challenge for young minds to learn, explore and discover the secrets of #DeepTech industry!</p> <p>The challenge is to propose a #businessidea that represent a real revolution for DeepTech areas, such as:</p> <p>#SpaceTech 🚀 #FoodTech 🍷 or #ClimateTech 🌱</p> <p>Learn more 📌 https://bit.ly/3V4bhAF</p> <p>We are waiting for you in Rimini from 15th to 17th of June! Apply today 📌 https://lnkd.in/ddDhUtSE</p>		1473865943654401
<p>📅 3 more days to apply 📅</p> <p>💡 #HackTheBusiness #hackathon 📌 https://lnkd.in/ddDhUtSE</p> <p>Don't miss your chance to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 🚀 Get full-access to the WMF - We Make Future event in Rimini, Italy! 🚀 Validate your #businessidea and network with investors. 🚀 Get selected for the ENTREPRENEDU mentoring & coaching programme and bring your business idea to the next level. 🚀 Win gadgets and more! <p>Let's #HackTheBusiness together! 🤝</p>	<p>HACKATHON</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7072208453498249216</p>

<p>🕒 2 more days to apply 📢</p> <p>😄 #HackTheBusiness</p> <p>💡 15-17 June Italy, Rimini WMF - We Make Future</p> <p>Haven't applied yet? What are you waiting for? Those ideas will not level-up on their own! 🚀</p> <p>Apply today 👉 https://lnkd.in/ddDhUtSE</p> <p>Let's #HackTheBusiness in Italy together! 🙌</p> <p>● ● ●</p>	<p>HACKATHON</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7072499362211274752</p>
<p>📢 Final day to apply and #HackTheBusiness in #Italy with us!</p> <p>💡 15-17 June Italy, Rimini WMF - We Make Future</p> <p>👉 https://lnkd.in/ddDhUtSE</p> <p>Don't miss the opportunity to network with investors, win prizes and level-up your business idea while having fun! 😄🙌</p> <p>● ● ●</p>	<p>HACKATHON</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7072889493887795200</p>
<p>🕒 Counting time until we #HackTheBusiness together in #Italy 📢</p> <p>Therefore, we invite you to take another look at the #ENTREPRENEDU website, meet the #HackTheBusiness team, download the #agenda and enjoy our #meme 😄</p> <p>Here's the shortcut 👉</p> <p>https://lnkd.in/dvcmDs-6</p> <p>● ● ●</p>	<p>HACKATHON</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7074427310241722368</p>

<p>Excitement level right now: </p>	<p>HACKATHON</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7074767091546910720</p>
<p>Welcome to the #HackTheBusiness, an event where you can level-up your business idea while having fun! 😄</p> <p></p>	<p>HACKATHON</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7075094008623976448</p>
<p>What a day for our #HackTheBusiness teams! 🧠</p> <p>While working on their #DeepTech ideas, they participated to 5 #workshops provided by #ENTREPRENEDEU experts and mentors, where they had a chance to learn about diverse #business tips and tricks:</p> <p>📁 Business Model Discovery Speaker: Katrin Singer-Coudoux,</p> <p>💡 Spark your success: Unleashing the brilliance within your ideas Speaker: Veronica Spadoni</p> <p>💰 Understanding Business Angels: Fundraising tips for startup founders Speaker: Jacopo Losso</p> <p>🎯 Building FUTUREPROOFED business ideas Speaker: Achilleas Barlas</p> <p>🙌 From idea to impact: Unlocking the potential of your business concepts Speaker: Ina Todorova</p>	<p>HACKATHON</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7075520406115229696</p>

<p>It seems that:</p> <p><i>"Learning never exhausts the mind."</i> - Leonardo da Vinci</p>		
<p>BREAKING NEWS:</p> <p>	<p>HACKATHON</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7075760367682908160</p>
<p>#HackTheBusiness #Italy AWARD CEREMONY 🏆</p> <p>What a day! After 72 hours of hacking, networking and having fun, we have our 4 winning teams! Big congratulations to all of them! 🥳</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> BOBIS <p>Teams - you showcased a lot of hard work and commitment for the past 3 days. We are proud of you! Well done! 🙌</p> <p><i>Thank you to all other participants: Don't give up from your great ideas!</i></p>	<p>HACKATHON</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7076106268515389440</p>

<p>Meet #HackTheBusiness #Italy winners! 🍷</p> <p>🚀 BOBIS 🚀</p> <p>Francesco, Paola, Jacopo and Stefano wish to ↘#CO2 #emissions caused by last mile logistics, offering the end user a #platform that can encourage #local consumption and the search for products and services within a distance of 3km 🙌</p> <p>We support them 100 percent! Congrats!</p>	<p>HACKATHON</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7076453557939380224</p>
<p>Meet #HackTheBusiness #Italy winners! 🍷</p> <p>🚀 AS YOU LIKE 🚀</p> <p>Federico Luigi, Vincenzo Tommaso, Giuseppe and Rodolfo Pietro wish to transform dining experience with a mobile app: customize meals, access real-time nutrition info with Visual-AI, and discover restaurants aligned with dietary needs - to make it all #asyoulike 🙌</p> <p>Well done! 😎</p>	<p>HACKATHON</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7076815960153677824</p>
<p>Meet #HackTheBusiness #Italy winners! 🍷</p> <p>🚀 SHADES OF BLUE 🚀</p> <p>Marijana and her team wish to create a certification system and consultancy services for #sustainable management of #water resources, providing companies monitoring, improving and communicating the negative impact on #rivers and water. 💡</p>	<p>HACKATHON</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7077211598213246976</p>

<p>Amazing! ❤️</p>		
<p>Meet #HackTheBusiness #Italy winners! 🥂</p> <p>🚀 BACKWARDS 🚀</p> <p>Dumitruta and Lorenzo are eager to solve the problem of #packaging waste by creating #reusablepackaging and #logistics infrastructure! ♻️</p> <p>Congratulations! 🙌 Great idea!</p>	<p>HACKATHON</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7077555837786808320</p>
<p>Not so long ago, we hacked the business in Italy! 😎</p> <p>#HackTheBusiness competition provided an ideal environment for fostering connections and #collaborations. 🤝 Participants had (and will have) the chance to #network with like-minded individuals, potential #investors, industry #influencers, and representatives from renowned organizations. 🙌</p> <p>This networking aspect enables them to build relationships, explore partnership #opportunities, gain exposure to a broader ecosystem of #innovation, experience & level-up professionally - all while having fun! 🥳</p> <p>Until the next #HackTheBusiness, here's a quick recap in a form of an #article and a #video!</p> <p>🔗 https://lnkd.in/eDvbB7-R</p> <p>👤 https://lnkd.in/eGNw3A7B</p>	<p>HACKATHON</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7080227878109376513</p>

<p>Time flies, indeed. 🕒 #ENTREPRENEDU team is already 6 months on a quest to enhance the entrepreneurial ecosystem for European education! 🎓👓🧐</p> <p>That's why we gathered in Rimini, to reflect on progress, share insights, and chart a course towards our goal! Here's a quick recap of the first ENTREPRENEDU General Assembly Meeting!</p> <p>🔗 https://lnkd.in/eW-ixHCF</p> <p>The biggest milestone so far was achieved, as we hacked the business in Italy, and as you can see below - we are super happy about it! 🥳</p> <p>Kudos to the team: Eleonora Lombardi Valerio Roscani, PhD Lorenzo Scatena Jacopo Losso Paola B. Christian Lechner Federica Brunetta Katrin Singer-Coudoux Henry Nicolai Buxmann Ina Todorova Achilleas Barlas Nektaria Berikou Jorge-A. Sanchez-P. Daniel Silva Anja Stipankov</p> <p>🟦🟡🟠</p>	<p>GENERAL ASSEMBLY IN RIMINI</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/posts/entreprenedu-entreprenedu-entreprenedu-horizon-eu-activity-7080494614779965440-4jr?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop</p>
<p>Okay... This post deserves a 🥁 Drumrolls, please 🥁 intro 😊</p>	<p>MEET EDU</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/fe</p>

<p>Why??? Because, it's time to meet EDU and get to know us (even) better! 😊</p> <p>So... Welcome to the ENTREPRENEDU world, full of fun and opportunities! 🙌 Take a 👁 at what we do:</p> <p>👤 https://lnkd.in/eQ2gs_Dp</p> <p>P.S. Do you know anyone who might be interested in joining us? Great! 🗨 Share the video with them or tag them below 🙌</p> <p>● ● ●</p>		<p>ed/update/urn:li:activity:7082345254787379201</p>
<p>It's Friday and #EDU is all packed and ready to start his #summertour around Europe! 🙌 His first stop is in Rome, Italy where he will meet our teammates from Fondazione E. Amaldi to go sightseeing #Colosseum 😊</p> <p>We wish you a happy #eurotrip, EDU! 😊</p> <p>Where do you think EDU will go next? Write is below! 🙌 #EDUsummertour</p> <p>● ● ●</p>	<p>EDU SUMMER TOUR</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7085542180336848896</p>
<p>Hey there, have you checked your inboxes yet? 📧</p> <p>P.S. Wish to stay up-to-date on #innovation and #entrepreneurship opportunities?</p> <p>Jump into #ENTREPRENEDU knowledge pool 📖</p> <p>👉 https://lnkd.in/eFX-b4Wi</p> <p>● ● ●</p>	<p>Newsletter #2</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7087415155038277632</p>
<p>#EDU is continuing his #summertour around Europe! 🗨</p> <p>Just today, he flew in Athens, Greece to join our teammates from Corallia and obviously, the first on their list was to go sightseeing #Acropolis 🙌</p>	<p>EDU SUMMER TOUR</p>	<p>https://twitter.com/entreprenedu/status/16823850796816</p>

<p>Do you have any recommendations what EDU should see next while in Athens? Write us! 📌</p> <p>Enjoy in Greece, EDU! 😊 #EDUsummertour</p> <p>●●●</p>		<p>46600</p>
<p>Our latest #pressrelease is online! 📄</p> <p>Once more, a round of applause for the #HackTheBusiness #Italy winners: BACKWARDS, SHADES OF BLUE, AS YOU LIKE & BOBIS 🙌🙌🙌🙌</p> <p>Read more at entrepreneu.eu 💡</p> <p>●●●</p>	<p>HackTheBusiness Italy After Event PR</p>	<p>/</p>
<p>Among sightseeing diverse attractions, #EDU also enjoys a nice adventure! This week, he is in Rila Mountain with our teammates from Cleantech Bulgaria on hiking! ▲</p> <p>EDU, send us more pictures, please! 📷</p> <p>●●●</p>	<p>EDU SUMMER TOUR</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7090609015457472513</p>
<p>🚀 [BREAKING NEWS] Fondazione E. Amaldi is pleased to invite its community to apply to the Call for Exhibitors to have the opportunity to be selected among the 20 startups that will be supported by Fondazione E. Amaldi and will have a booth for free in the Maker Faire Rome- The European Edition organised by Camera di Commercio Roma on 20-22 October 2023 in Rome.</p> <p>🚀 You will also have the chance to boost your business getting in touch with experts, innovators and entrepreneurs and be part of the Space Arena organized by Fondazione E. Amaldi in the Maker Faire Rome- The European Edition Expo area.</p> <p>💡 Are you a European innovative startup that integrates space technologies and data? Apply to the Call for Exhibitors by 20th September 2023 to make a difference in the European innovation landscape! 📌 → https://rb.gy/23vo3</p>	<p>RePost from FEA</p>	<p>/</p>

<p>✉ For any further information contact us at: eventi@fondazioneamaldi.it</p>		
<p>If you are thinking about diving into the world of #entrepreneurship and you don't know where to start, we recommend you this #podcast 💡</p>	<p>RePost from AccelerAction Project</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7092142422712852480</p>
<p>After an adventurous detour in Bulgaria, #EDU is back in Greece! 🌟 He is saying #hi from Meteora, where he's together with our teammates from University of Thessaly 🤝</p> <p>#Hi back to you, EDU! 🙌</p> <p></p>	<p>EDU SUMMER TOUR</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7093136649286524928</p>
<p>This Friday, #EDU is greeting us from Berlin where he met our teammates from Fraunhofer IPK 🤝</p> <p>Enjoy in Germany, EDU! 📷</p> <p></p>	<p>EDU SUMMER TOUR</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7095699932824690689</p>
<p>After he had a great time in Berlin 📷 #EDU is in Brussels, Belgium to meet our teammates from EBAN - European Business Angel Network 🤝</p> <p>Any recommendations for EDU while in Brussels? Write us in the comments and we will transfer the message! 🙌</p> <p></p>	<p>EDU SUMMER TOUR</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7097884766372265984</p>
<p>From Belgium to Ireland, #EDU is in Dublin to meet our teammates from F6S Innovation 🤝 P.S. We are not quite sure way, but we have a feeling that EDU will enjoy his time in Dublin! 😊</p> <p>Happy weekend everyone! 🙌</p> <p></p>	<p>EDU SUMMER TOUR</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7100830175772180480</p>

<p>#EDU had the greatest time while traveling around #Europe and meeting #ENTREPRENEDU teammates. 🙌 At his very last stop, he is meeting Luiss Guido Carli University team at the #TreviFountain 📍</p> <p>EDU, thank you for sharing with us your #EuroTrip 🇮🇹 Until the next adventure, #arrivederci! 🙌</p> <p>●●●</p>	<p>EDU SUMMER TOUR</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7103298747081588736</p>
<p>Great opportunity for young entrepreneurs is on #ENTREPRENEDU radar 🔍👉</p>	<p>Reshare</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7104766530810261504</p>
<p>The countdown has officially begun for the launch of the second #HackTheBusiness competition by #ENTREPRENEDU! Whether you're a student with an idea or a professional with a vision, this is your ticket to explore the unknown realms of innovation. Stay tuned for an interstellar journey! 🚀</p>	<p>HTB Greece</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7105151352422432769</p>
<p>Take your creativity beyond the stratosphere! Prepare for a journey filled with innovation, inspiration, and (of course) fun! 🚀🌍 #SpaceEntrepreneurs</p>	<p>HTB Greece</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7105862040107298817</p>
<p>Ready to take off into the world of #SpaceTech? 🚀 #HackTheBusiness contest is here to launch your #startup dreams. 🙌</p> <p>P.S. Can you guess who has already joined the journey? 🙌</p> <p>●●●</p>	<p>HTB Greece</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7106939219188592642</p>
<p>#HackTheBusiness Greece is the 2nd event in the ENTREPRENEDU #hackathons series. The 1st one was held in Italy! Let's hear our participants and their thoughts on #HackTheBusiness experience 🙌</p>	<p>HTB Greece</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7108479162595602432</p>
<p>✉️ @ENTREPRENEDU newsletter is out in the email-world! Missed it! Subscribe and stay in the knowledge loop 🧠</p>	<p>NL #3</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7112</p>

<p>http://eepurl.com/ilqOzv</p>		<p>037642610876417</p>
<p>Interested in hacking the business in Greece with us? Read all about #HackTheBusiness competition in our newest PR article!</p>	<p>HTB Greece PR</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7112040205120868352</p>
<p>🇪🇺 #EDU is in the #spacesuit, that must be a sign 🙌 Registrations for #HackTheBusiness #Greece competition are officially open! 🇪🇺</p> <p>If you are from 18 to 40 years old, don't miss the chance to become our next #HackTheBusiness participant and #win the full support of the ENTREPRENEDU expert team! ⭐</p> <p>We will help you to turn your #idea into successful #startup! 🙌 So, take your chance and hack the business in Greece with us! 🙌 https://lnkd.in/eRkhznSK</p> <p></p> <p>#ENTREPRENEDU #HorizonEU #EUIInnovationEcosystems #innovation #entrepreneurship #education #students #startups #spaceentrepreneurs #spaceinnovation #space #HackTheBusiness #Greece</p>	<p>HTB Greece - SCHEDULED</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7114896928688979969</p>
<p>Ready to launch your #startup idea into orbit? 🚀 Provide us with an innovative #solution around #SPACE and you will have a chance to win full #mentorship programme organised by ENTREPRENEDU team! 🙌</p> <p>Our goal is to turn your idea into a #successful startup! 😎 Wait no more - apply for the most #exciting space-themed competition in Greece! 🙌</p> <p>More information at https://lnkd.in/eRkhznSK</p> <p></p> <p>#ENTREPRENEDU #HorizonEU #EUIInnovationEcosystems #innovation #entrepreneurship #education #students #startups #spaceentrepreneurs #spaceinnovation #space #HackTheBusiness #Greece</p>	<p>HTB Greece - SCHEDULED</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7115259266139074560</p>
<p>Discover all the benefits of participating in #HackTheBusiness competition! ✨ Find out more: https://lnkd.in/e4tSQ9Fz</p>	<p>HTB Greece -</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7115259266139074560</p>

<p>P.S. Your entrepreneurial journey could start today! 🚀 Apply to #HackTheBusiness in Greece 📌 https://lnkd.in/eRkhznSK</p> <p>●●●</p> <p>#ENTREPRENEDU #HorizonEU #EUInnovationEcosystems #innovation #entrepreneurship #education #students #startups #spaceentrepreneurs #spaceinnovation #space #HackTheBusiness #Greece</p>	<p>SCHEDULED</p>	<p>ed/update/urn:li:activity:7115614102336495616</p>
<p>You are amazed by #SPACE? 🌑 We are, too! 😎 That's why we are organising a #HackTheBusiness competition where you (and your team) can showcase your space-idea and win up to 60 hours of business #coaching and #mentoring by #ENTREPRENEDU experts!</p> <p>Don't miss a chance to get our #support and become #SPACEInnovator! We are waiting for you! 📌</p> <p>Read all about it at https://lnkd.in/eRkhznSK</p> <p>●●●</p> <p>#ENTREPRENEDU #HorizonEU #EUInnovationEcosystems #innovation #entrepreneurship #education #students #startups #spaceentrepreneurs #spaceinnovation #space #HackTheBusiness #Greece</p>	<p>HTB Greece - SCHEDULED</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7117433593387208704</p>
<p>Explore the future of #SPACE technologies! 📺 Get inspired to #HackTheBusiness with us and discover #top #trends that are reshaping the space sector! 📺</p> <p>📺 https://lnkd.in/eCnfh7Wh</p> <p>P.S. Your space-adventure is waiting for you! Apply today! 📌 https://lnkd.in/eRkhznSK</p>	<p>HTB Greece - SCHEDULED</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7118158375606972416</p>

<p>#ENTREPRENEU #HorizonEU #EUIInnovationEcosystems #innovation #entrepreneurship #education #students #startups #spaceentrepreneurs #spaceinnovation #space #HackTheBusiness #Greece #SpaceTechTrends #FutureOfSpace</p>		
<p>Wish to learn how to #HackTheBusiness in #Greece and meet other potential participants? 🤔 Prepare a list of questions and tune in to the #ENTREPRENEU warm-up events on October 18 and 25 to learn all about the competition and space trends. 📝</p> <p>The goal is to get inspired and potentially "catch" your winning idea! ✨</p> <p>Warm-up event #1 "The Greek space ecosystem" 	<p>HTB Greece - Warm-up events</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7119690396204433408</p>
<p>Buckle up for the ultimate space-inspired competition! 🚀 Whether you're a #student with an idea or a #professional with a vision, this is your ticket to explore the unknown realms of innovation. ✨</p>	<p>HTB Greece - SCHEDULED</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7119690396204433408</p>

<p>ENTREPRENEDU #mentors will be there on every step to guide you and provide you support! 😊 Don't miss the #opportunity! Exciting and fun space-adventure is waiting for you! 🚀</p> <p>Find out more at https://lnkd.in/eRkhznSK</p> <p></p> <p>#ENTREPRENEDU #HorizonEU #EUIInnovationEcosystems #innovation #entrepreneurship #education #students #startups #spaceentrepreneurs #spaceinnovation #space #HackTheBusiness #Greece</p>		<p>9970368982761473</p>
<p></p>	<p>HTB Greece - Warm-up events</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7120314588050395136</p>
<p>The first #HackTheBusiness warm-up event is over! 🎬 Potential participants had a chance to learn more about ENTREPRENEDU, the structure of the competition, space-challenge, ask questions and network. 😎</p> <p>Missed it? No worries, the second warm-up event is scheduled for next Wednesday! 🙌</p>	<p>HTB Greece - Warm-up events</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7120435584048734208</p>

<p>Warm-up event #2 "Success stories from Greek space start-ups" 		
<p>Competing to win? 🏆 Discover why having a #mentor can be your ultimate game-changer in competitions! <p>#ENTREPRENEDEDU #HorizonEU #EUIInnovationEcosystems #innovation #entrepreneurship #education #students #startups #spaceentrepreneurs #spaceinnovation #space #HackTheBusiness #Greece #mentorship</p>	<p>HTB Greece - SCHEDULED</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7120695099319037952</p>
<p>Interested to #HackTheBusiness with us but missing some answers?! That's okay! 😊 Join the second #HackTheBusiness warm-up event organised by #ENTREPRENEDEDU team and remove all doubts! 🙌</p> <p>Warm-up event #2 "Success stories from Greek space start-ups" 16:00-18:00 CET</p> <p>Join us 🙌 https://lnkd.in/d-VNAXpd</p>	<p>HTB Greece - Warm-up events</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7122207492670971904</p>

<p>Let's #HackTheBusiness together!</p>		
<p>The first phase of the #HackTheBusiness ideation contest is approaching rapidly and the excitement level is rising! 🤖🚀</p> <p>The first phase will be held on 3-5 November across Greece, in collaboration with 5 Greek Universities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● MOKE Πανεπιστημίου Θεσσαλίας, University of Thessaly ● National Technical University of Athens ● Πολυτεχνείο Κρήτης - Technical University of Crete ● Democritus University of Thrace - (D.U.Th.) ● Walk _ AUTH Innovation Accelerator, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH) <p>Join us and hack the business in Greece with #EDU and the rest of the #ENTREPRENEDU team! 🙌</p> <p>Register today, it's easy: https://lnkd.in/eRkhznSK</p>	<p>HTB Greece</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7122519020007829504</p>
<p>🚀🔥🚀 Don't miss the last #HackTheBusiness warm-up event! 🙌</p> <p>Warm-up event #2 "Success stories from Greek space start-ups"</p> <p>📅 25.10.2023. 🕒 16:00-18:00 CET</p> <p>This is your chance to learn more about the competition, Greek #spaceinnovation ecosystem, and ask all of your questions! ✅</p> <p>Join us 🙌</p>	<p>HTB Greece - Warm-up events</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7122861590063816705</p>

<p>https://lnkd.in/d-VNAXpd</p> <p>Let's #HackTheBusiness together!</p> <p></p>		
<p>We have successfully closed both warm-up sessions organised by the #ENTREPRENEDU team! 🙌</p> <p>Thank you to all participants for attention and participation and see you soon in #Greece!</p> <p>Let's #HackTheBusiness together! 🚀</p> <p>Apply now, it's easy 🙌</p> <p></p>	<p>HTB Greece - Warm-up events</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7122973788039708672</p>
<p> To recap:</p> <p>#HackTheBusiness is the ideation contest for curious minds to learn, explore and discover secrets of #space! 🚀 The competition will unfold in two phases:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The first phase will be held on 3-5 November across Greece, in collaboration with 5 Greek Universities. ● First phase #winners will get a #free ticket to the Finals in Athens on November 25, and pitch their idea to #ENTREPRENEDU experts. 	<p>HTB Greece</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7123300782547816448</p>

<p>💡 Remember:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● You should be between #18 and #40 years old. ● You don't have to know anything about space. Our mentors will be there on every step to guide you! 🔥 ● You can join us as an #individual or as a part of the #team! <p>🎁 The prize:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The 4 winning finalists (teams) will receive valuable #prizes and a dedicated #mentorship programme organised by #ENTREPRENEDU experts, where they will learn all perks of #business and have a chance to become #SpaceInnovators! <p>Join the adventure! 🔗👉 https://lnkd.in/eRkhznSK</p> <p>●●●</p>		
<p>Missed both Warm-up events (🤔), but you still want to know all the details about the upcoming #HackTheBusiness competition in #Greece? We got you covered! 😊</p> <p>Presenting ENTREPRENEDU #youtube #playlist where you will find warm-up events' recordings! 🙌</p> <p>Get inspired and learn how to #HackTheBusiness with us! 🎥👁️ https://lnkd.in/dz6kj_R8</p> <p>●●●</p>	<p>HTB Greece - Warm-up events recordings</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7123686337248976896</p>
<p>🕒🕒🕒 3 DAYS 🕒🕒🕒</p> <p>Don't miss the #HackTheBusiness adventure, register today:👉 https://lnkd.in/eRkhznSK</p> <p>P.S. Due to the high interest, we are organising the third warm-up event! 🙌 This is your final chance to ask questions about this exciting contest! ✅</p>	<p>HTB Greece - Warm-up event #3</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7124763072379969536</p>

<p>📅 1.11.2023. 🕒 17:00-18:00 CET</p> <p>Link to join the warm-up event 📌 https://lnkd.in/dSM9mZyv</p> <p>Let's #HackTheBusiness together! 🚀</p> <p>● ● ●</p>		
<p>🚀🚀🚀🚀 2 DAYS 🚀🚀🚀🚀</p> <p>Step 1: Register 📌 https://lnkd.in/eRkhznSK</p> <p>Step 2: Unlock the secrets to building a #winning team 📌 https://lnkd.in/dc3MV5nf</p> <p>Step 3: #HackTheBusiness in Greece with us 🚀</p> <p>● ● ●</p>	<p>HTB Greece 2 DAYS</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7125043738615197696</p>
<p>🚀🚀🚀🚀 1 DAY 🚀🚀🚀🚀</p> <p>Register now, it's easy 📌 https://lnkd.in/eRkhznSK</p> <p>You can join us as an #individual or as a part of the #team, #HackTheBusiness in Greece and turn your #idea into a real #startup! 🚀 And if you are still not ¹⁰⁰ percent sure whether you should participate or not, join us today at the last warm-up event where we will talk more about the challenge, concept of the competition and of course - prizes. 🎁</p> <p>Link to join the warm-up event 📌 https://lnkd.in/dSM9mZyv</p>	<p>HTB Greece 1 DAY</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7125419333899407360</p>

<p>Let's #HackTheBusiness together! 🚀</p> <p>●●●</p>		
<p>📺 We are live 📺 Don't miss the last warm-up event, where our teammate Orfeas Voutyras from Corallia is answering to all of your questions and sharing useful #tips and #tricks on how to #HackTheBusiness in Greece 😊</p> <p>Link to join the warm-up event 📌 https://lnkd.in/dSM9mZyv</p> <p>Still not registered? Register now and #HackTheBusiness with us! 🚀 https://lnkd.in/dAx83EQv</p> <p>●●●</p>	<p>Warm-Up Event #3</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7125521745784025090</p>
<p>🚀🚀🚀 LAST DAY 🚀🚀🚀</p> <p>📌 https://lnkd.in/dAx83EQv</p> <p>The start of #HackTheBusiness challenge is just around the corner and we are super exciting about it! 📺</p> <p>#HackTheBusiness is the ideation contest for curious minds to learn, explore and discover secrets of #space! 📌 Remember, you actually don't have to know anything about space. #ENTREPRENEDU mentors will be there on every step to guide you! 🔥</p> <p>Register and join us in this exciting #space adventure! ● https://lnkd.in/dAx83EQv</p> <p>●●●</p>	<p>HTB Greece LAST DAY</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7125780806081363968</p>
<p>We are ready to #HackTheBusiness in Greece! 😊🚀📺</p> <p>#ENTREPRENEDU team wishes the best of luck to all participants! We hope you will enjoy this space-adventure! 🌱</p>	<p>HTB Greece START</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7126201579220664323</p>

<p>#ENTREPRENEDU team sends a big #congratulations to all participants who managed to #HackTheBusiness in #Greece this weekend! 🎉 Well done, teams, there were so many great space-ideas showcased! 🚀</p> <p>Next steps 📌</p> <p>Winning teams will now have time to enhance their #ideas even more with the support of our #mentors, before we all meet again, on November 25 in #Athens, for the big #finals. 🚀 #staytuned</p>	<p>HTB Greece Congratulation s</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7127643418826002432</p>
<p>ENTREPRENEDU team marked a #successful start of the second #HackTheBusiness competition, this time in Greece! 🎉</p> <p>https://lnkd.in/d/S5PYCRh</p> <p>In this special article, we are revealing our #finalists and showcasing #backstage moments from the first phase of the competition.</p> <p>Once again, congratulations to all participants! 🎉</p> <p>P.S. Kudos to hardworking organisers Corallia ΜΟΚΕ Πανεπιστημίου Θεσσαλίας, University of Thessaly National Technical University of Athens Democritus University of Thrace - (D.U.Th.) Walk _ AUTH Innovation Accelerator, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH) Πολυτεχνείο Κρήτης - Technical University of Crete Fondazione E. Amaldi Fraunhofer IPK EBAN - European Business Angel Network F6S Innovation Luiss Guido Carli University Cleantech Bulgaria</p>	<p>HTB Greece Blog post 1st phase</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7128317848279527424</p>
<p>🔍 Interesting opportunity on ENTREPRENEDU's radar 🔍</p> <p>Don't miss the chance to apply for South3E - S3E Charge, the accelerator program for #startups in their #growth phase developing innovative #DeepTech products and services 🚀</p>	<p>S3E Collaboration</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7130846491702632448</p>

<p>🕒 Applications close on 15 December 2023 📌 Find all the information here: https://lnkd.in/dt8BYgBn</p> <p>#EntrepreneurshipEngine #S3E #DeepTech #S3Eopencall</p>		
<p>Exciting news 🎉</p> <p>ENTREPRENEDU team will be present at NSE ExpoForum 2023 - the international exhibition and conference that highlights the extraordinary potential of the new #space economy! 🚀</p> <p>🌐 It is a vibrant hub for technology transfer, connecting #innovators and industry #leaders to discover breakthrough ideas, explore potential applications and demonstrate how cutting-edge space technology fuels innovation and growth in sectors such as transportation, agriculture, telecommunications, healthcare and more!</p> <p>See you at Fiera Roma 5-6-7 December 2023! 🤝</p> <p>If you wish to join us, don't forget to get your conference pass! 📌 https://lnkd.in/gCSg_KP</p> <p>🟡🟠🔴</p>	<p>NSE collaboration</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7131209540221440001</p>
<p>📅 The final countdown has begun! 📅</p> <p>5 more days until we meet in Athens, for the #HackTheBusiness #Greece Grand Final! 🤝👏🎉</p> <p>In the #Finals, winning teams of the first phase of the #HackTheBusiness competition will present their #space business solutions to the jury and compete for valuable prizes! 🎁</p> <p>For example - the exclusive access to the dedicated ENTREPRENEDU Mentoring & Coaching Programme, in which our winning teams will receive necessary know-how to turn their #ideas into real #startups! Not bad, right? 😊</p>	<p>HTB Greece The Final countdown</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7132289750710820865</p>

<p>Let's #HackTheBusiness 🚀</p> <p>🟡🟠🔴</p>		
<p>📢 The final countdown has begun! 📢</p> <p>3 more days until we meet in Athens, for the #HackTheBusiness #Greece Grand Final! 🙌👏👏</p> <p>Take a look at our preliminary #agenda and meet #organisers #speakers and #jury members by clicking the link below 📌</p> <p>🔗 https://lnkd.in/eRkhznSK</p> <p>Let's #HackTheBusiness 🚀</p> <p>🟡🟠🔴</p>	<p>HTB Greece The Final countdown</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7133108574787883009</p>
<p>📢 1 day to go 📢</p> <p>See you tomorrow in Athens, for the #HackTheBusiness #Greece Grand Final! 🙌👏</p> <p>P.S. Dear participants, until we meet, think about this special meme 📌🕶️</p> <p>https://entrepredu.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/08/Meme.png</p> <p>Let's #HackTheBusiness 🚀</p> <p>🟡🟠🔴</p>	<p>HTB Greece The Final countdown</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7133741067459280896</p>
<p>📢 Hey, have you heard the news? We hacked the business in Greece!</p> <p>Last weekend, innovation, ambition, and inspiration were in the air at the #HackTheBusiness #Finals at Corallia premises in Athens, Greece!</p>	<p>HTB Greece Finals</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7134897461684240384</p>

<p>Once again, #HackTheBusiness brought together students and young professionals who had a wish to turn their ideas into a real startup! 🌟</p> <p>The stakes were high as our participants pitched for a spot in the exclusive ENTREPRENEDU Mentoring & Coaching Programme and additional valuable prizes. 🏆</p> <p>#ENTREPRENEDU team sends thank you notes to all organisers, mentors, sponsors and participants for their amazing efforts! ✨</p> <p>Special thank you note goes to Hellenic Ministry of Digital Governance and Mr. Konstantinos Kyranakis, Deputy Minister of Digital Governance in Greece!</p> <p>#StayTuned, we are announcing winners soon!</p> <p>🟦🟡🟠</p>		
<p>Read all about #HackTheBusiness #Greece #Finals in our newest #PR article! 📰</p> <p>🟦🟡🟠</p>	<p>HTB Greece Finals PR</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7134903460444930048</p>
<p>Meet #HackTheBusiness #Greece winners! 🥂</p> <p>🚀 GROUNDWATER 🚀</p> <p>Congratulations team and welcome to the ENTREPRENEDU Mentoring & Coaching Programme where your innovative idea has a strong potential to become a real startup! 😎</p> <p>🟦🟡🟠</p>	<p>HTB Greece Finals Meet the Winners</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7135272516876460034</p>
<p>Meet #HackTheBusiness #Greece winners! 🥂</p> <p>🏆 GROUNDWATER 🏆 UNIWA ICE</p>	<p>HTB Greece Finals Meet the Winners</p>	<p>/</p>

<p>🏆 EXKE 🏆 MICROSATLAB</p> <p>Congratulations team and welcome to the ENTREPRENEDEDU Mentoring & Coaching Programme where your innovative idea has a strong potential to become a real startup! 😎</p> <p>You hacked the business! 🚀</p> <p>● ● ●</p>		
<p>Meet #HackTheBusiness #Greece winners! 🥂</p> <p>🚀 UNIWA ICE 🚀</p> <p>Congratulations team and welcome to the ENTREPRENEDEDU Mentoring & Coaching Programme where your innovative idea has a strong potential to become a real startup! 😎</p> <p>● ● ●</p>	<p>HTB Greece Finals Meet the Winners</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7135592971541917698</p>
<p>Meet #HackTheBusiness #Greece winners! 🥂</p> <p>🚀 EXKE 🚀</p> <p>Congratulations team and welcome to the ENTREPRENEDEDU Mentoring & Coaching Programme where your innovative idea has a strong potential to become a real startup! 😎</p> <p>● ● ●</p>	<p>HTB Greece Finals Meet the Winners</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7135986463988404226</p>
<p>Meet #HackTheBusiness #Greece winners! 🥂</p> <p>🚀 MICROSATLAB 🚀</p>	<p>HTB Greece Finals Meet the Winners</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7136277761345699842</p>

<p>Congratulations team and welcome to the ENTREPRENEDU Mentoring & Coaching Programme where your innovative idea has a strong potential to become a real startup! 🙌</p> <p>🟡🟢🔴</p>		
<p>Guess what we did 10 days ago? We hacked the business in Greece! 🙌</p> <p>Here's the quick recap 📌</p> <p>👁️ https://lnkd.in/dqHbJkpu</p> <p>Once more, big #congratulations to all teams! 🙌</p> <p>🟡🟢🔴</p>	<p>HTB Greece Finals Video</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7137856308434599937</p>
<p>We are beyond proud of all #HackTheBusiness participants. Thank you for joining the #ENTREPRENEDU journey. We are sure it will be fun 🙌 and insightful! 💡</p> <p>P.S.</p> <p>#HackTheBusiness #Greece article is now available at entreprenedu.eu 🙌</p> <p>Here's the shortcut ➡️ https://entreprenedu.eu/they-hacked-the-business-in-greece-meet-the-winners/</p> <p>🟡🟢🔴</p>	<p>HTB Greece Finals Blog Article</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7138473036567015425</p>
<p>What is considered under #ENTREPRENEDU Mentoring & Coaching Programme? 🙌 Learn it all in the article below 📌</p> <p>https://lnkd.in/ePKMiJug</p> <p>🟡🟢🔴</p>	<p>ENTREPRENEDU Mentoring & Coaching Programme</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7141436550734610432</p>
<p>Warm regards from the ENTREPRENEDU second #GeneralAssembly meeting!</p>	<p>General</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/</p>

<p>#ENTREPRENEDEU team marked 12 months in this exciting journey! 🎉🎊 ⌚ It seems that time flies when you are working & having fun. 🙌</p> <p>●●●</p>	<p>Assembly Online</p>	<p>ed/update/urn:li:activity:714326989213633312</p>
<p>#HappyHolidays, future entrepreneurs! 🎓🚀☀️</p> <p>Wishing you a break filled with relaxation, joy, and heaps of inspiration for your entrepreneurial journey ahead. 🎁💡 Here's to dreaming big and aiming high in the coming year! 🌲☀️</p> <p>#ENTREPRENEDEU team</p> <p>P.S. Can you guess who is our #Santa? 😊</p> <p>●●●</p>	<p>Happy Holidays</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7144997919195111424</p>
<p>🎉🚀 New year, new updates!</p> <p>Jump into the #ENTREPRENEDEU knowledge pool and stay ahead of the curve in #2024! Don't miss out on the journey to success - join others and subscribe now! ☀️</p> <p>✉️ http://eepurl.com/ilqOzv</p> <p>●●●</p>	<p>NEWSLETTER SUBSCRIPTION</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7148598975875465216</p>
<p>✉️ ENTREPRENEDEU #newsletter is out in the email-world! Missed it? 😊 Subscribe and stay in the knowledge loop 🧠</p> <p>👍👍👍 http://eepurl.com/ilqOzv</p> <p>●●●</p>	<p>NEWSLETTER #4</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7151495801628704768</p>

<p>We would love to add one more tip: → Don't miss the final #HackTheBusiness ideation competition organised by #ENTREPRENEDU team! 🔥 It will give you everything you need for a sleek start in the business world. 📢 #staytuned</p> <p>👁️ https://lnkd.in/e27H3t6w</p> <p>●●●</p>	<p>Sharing advices</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7153003706911760384</p>
<p>If you are not quite sure what #ENTREPRENEDU project is about, take a look at this short story about #EDU and get to know us better! 😊</p> <p>👁️ https://lnkd.in/eiwusAym</p> <p>●●●</p>	<p>Recap</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7156211095358087168</p>
<p>Are you ready for the final round? 📢 #StayTuned</p> <p>●●●</p>	<p>HTB BULGARIA</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7160920147174522880</p>
<p>Dreaming of a #sustainable world? 🌍 Transform your ideas into solutions and #HackTheBusiness with us in #Bulgaria 📢 #StayTuned for a #green adventure! 😊</p> <p>●●●</p>	<p>HTB BULGARIA</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:716275810446753792</p>
<p>Have a business idea? Make it a reality with your startup! #HackTheBusiness with us in #Bulgaria and digitize your way to a greener future. 🚀🌍</p> <p>●●●</p>	<p>HTB BULGARIA</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:71627322384916152322</p>
<p>This #ValentinesDay, our hearts at #ENTREPRENEDU are captivated by #green & #sustainable ideas! 💡🌱📢 Have a brilliant one? Share it below and let's inspire a sustainable future together!</p>	<p>HTB BULGARIA</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7163457057113784321</p>
<p>📢 #EDU is here to give a sign that registrations for #HackTheBusiness #Bulgaria competition are officially open! 📢</p> <p>We are looking for innovative & sustainable ideas related to #digital & #creative industries, #construction, #agrifood and #manufacturing 🌱</p>	<p>HTB BULGARIA</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7167799203203641344</p>

<p>If you are from 18 to 40 years old, don't miss the chance of becoming our next #HackTheBusiness participant, winning the full support of the #ENTREPRENEDEDU experts and turning your #idea into a #startup!★</p> <p>Take your chance and hack the business in Bulgaria with us! 📌 https://entreprenedu.eu/hackthebusinessbulgaria/</p> <p></p>		
<p>Wanna #HackTheBusiness in #Bulgaria but not really sure how? 😬 We got you! 🤓 Join our </p>	<p>HTB BULGARIA info webinar</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7168211779930570753</p>
<p>Read all about the final #HackTheBusiness competition in our newest #PR article! 🔗 https://lnkd.in/es4G2JFp</p>	<p>HTB BULGARIA PR</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7168211779930570753</p>

<p>🔔 REGISTRATIONS OPEN 🔔 https://lnkd.in/e6nFGmcV</p> <p>P.S. Join our i INFO WEBINAR: Innovating for a sustainable future: HackTheBusiness Bulgaria revealed 🌱 and learn how to #HackTheBusiness 🙌 https://lnkd.in/e-j5Ucsu</p> <p>Let's #HackTheBusiness for a sustainable future!</p> <p>● ● ●</p>		<p>8555833813889025</p>
<p>🔔 REGISTRATIONS OPEN 🔔 Interested in hacking the business in Bulgaria with us? 😎</p> <p>Read more: https://entrepredu.eu/lets-hackthebusiness-in-bulgaria-for-a-sustainable-future/</p> <p>P.S. Join our i INFO WEBINAR: Innovating for a sustainable future: HackTheBusiness Bulgaria revealed 🌱 https://www.f6s.com/hackthebusiness-bulgaria-webinar/about</p> <p>● ● ●</p>	<p>HTB BULGARIA Article</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7168877659454709761</p>
<p>Are you interested in @ENTREPRENEDU #HackTheBusiness #Bulgaria but have some questions about the event? Join i INFO WEBINAR: Innovating for a sustainable future: HackTheBusiness Bulgaria revealed 🌱 https://www.f6s.com/hackthebusiness-bulgaria-webinar/about</p> <p>We'll be there to answer all of your questions! 😎 Ready to #HackTheBusiness? Apply for the #green adventure and make a world a better place! ❤️ https://entrepredu.eu/hackthebusinessbulgaria/ ● ● ●</p>	<p>HTB BULGARIA Webinar + registration</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7170361930199605248</p>
<p>Join us for a one hour i INFO WEBINAR to learn all about how to #HackTheBusiness in Bulgaria and have your questions answered by the organising team. ✅</p> <p>Innovating for a sustainable future: HackTheBusiness Bulgaria revealed 🌱📅 March 7 15h CET Online https://lnkd.in/e-j5Ucsu</p>	<p>HTB BULGARIA Webinar + registration</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7170730677099819008</p>

<p>P.S. Already ready to #HackTheBusiness? Apply for the #green adventure today 🙌 https://lnkd.in/e6nFGmcV</p> <p>●●●</p>		
<p>📅 1 DAY TO GO 📺 📺 INFO WEBINAR: Innovating for a sustainable future: HackTheBusiness Bulgaria revealed 🌱</p> <p>📅 March 7 15h CET Online</p> <p>Register now 🔗 https://lnkd.in/e-j5Ucsu</p> <p>In there, you will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Have an overview of the #sustainability challenges - Get to know more about #HackTheBusiness opportunity - Listen to #success story from previous #HackTheBusiness edition - Listen to #success story from the #local ecosystem - Ask all of your #questions during the Q&A session <p>🔗 https://lnkd.in/e-j5Ucsu</p> <p>🙌 The goal of the #Webinar is to provide you with all the information you need to know before participating in the #HackTheBusiness competition, and give you a chance to meet the organisers and other participants! 😎</p> <p>P.S. Already ready to #HackTheBusiness? ✓ Apply today!</p> <p>📱 https://lnkd.in/e6nFGmcV</p> <p>●●●</p>	<p>HTB BULGARIA Webinar + registration</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:717110482148352000</p>
<p>We are live at 📺 INFO WEBINAR: Innovating for a sustainable future: HackTheBusiness Bulgaria revealed 🌱</p> <p>Couldn't join and you really wanted to learn all about how to #HackTheBusiness in Bulgaria? 😞 Don't worry, we will publish the recording soon! #staytuned</p>	<p>HTB BULGARIA Webinar + registration</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7171510265165918209</p>

<p>P.S. Already ready to #HackTheBusiness? ✓ Apply today! https://lnkd.in/e6nFGmcV</p> <p>●●●</p>		
<p>Hey wannabe #entrepreneurs, got a brilliant idea for a sustainable future? 🌱 Join us in Bulgaria and #HackTheBusiness! Sounds interesting? Learn all about the event directly from organisers 👉 https://lnkd.in/eZgpviW3</p> <p>Ready to change the world? ❤️ Register today! https://lnkd.in/e6nFGmcV</p> <p>●●●</p>	<p>HTB BULGARIA Webinar recording + registration</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7172982320826683392</p>
<p>We are looking for innovative & sustainable ideas related to #digital & #creative industries, #construction, #agrifood and #manufacturing 🌱</p> <p>If you are from 18 to 40 years old, don't miss the chance to become our next #HackTheBusiness participant, get the full support of the #ENTREPRENEDEDU experts and turn your #idea into a #startup! ⭐</p> <p>Registrations are open! https://entreprenedu.eu/hackthebusinessbulgaria/</p> <p>●●●</p>	<p>HTB BULGARIA registration</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7173248185178533888</p>
<p>REPOST FROM EISMEA</p>	<p>HTB BULGARIA registration</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7173649551466151937</p>
<p>Having a mentor by your side provides guidance, builds confidence, offers networking opportunities, and fosters personal and professional growth. 🙌 Their expertise and support can make all the difference in your journey to success. 🏆</p> <p>#HackTheBusiness with us in #Bulgaria and let #ENTREPRENEDEDU mentors help you unlock your full potential and achieve your goals! 🎯</p> <p>Registrations are open! https://entreprenedu.eu/hackthebusinessbulgaria/</p>	<p>HTB BULGARIA registration</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7174007117811437568</p>

<p>Read more 👉 https://entreprenedu.eu/the-role-of-mentorship-in-.../</p>		
<p>Have an innovative & sustainable idea related to #digital & #creative industries, #construction, #agrifood or #manufacturing? Your innovation could be the change we've been waiting for. 🌟❤️</p> <p>As #HackTheBusiness participant you could win the full support of the #ENTREPRENEDU experts who will be there along the way to support your sustainable dream!</p> <p>Registrations are open until 25th of March 2024 - secure your spot today!</p> <p>🔗 https://entreprenedu.eu/hackthebusinessbulgaria/</p>	<p>HTB BULGARIA registration</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7174354798803091456</p>
<p>🔔🔔🔔 7 DAYS 🔔🔔🔔</p> <p>Yes... 7 more days to register and use the opportunity to turn your sustainable #idea into a real #startup! 🕶️</p> <p>🔗 https://www.f6s.com/entreprenedu-hackthebusinessbulgaria/apply</p> <p>🔄 To recap:</p> <p>#HackTheBusiness is the ideation contest for curious minds to learn and explore the wide potential of #sustainability 🌱 and #digitalisation 🌐 The competition will take place in Sofia, Bulgaria.</p> <p>💡 Remember:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 🔵 You should be between #18 and #40 years old. 🔵 You don't have to have a prior experience nor immediate idea. Our mentors will be there on every step to guide you and inspire you! 🌟 🔵 You can join us as an #individual or as a part of the #team! <p>🎁 The prize:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 🔵 Winning teams will receive valuable #prizes and a dedicated #mentorship programme organised by #ENTREPRENEDU experts, where have a chance to become #startup founders! 	<p>HTB BULGARIA registration 7 days</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7175490361589403650</p>

<p>Join our green, eco-adventure! ❤️ https://www.f6s.com/entreprenedu-hackthebusinessbulgaria/apply</p> <p>● ● ●</p>		
<p>🕒 5 DAYS 🕒 Don't miss the #HackTheBusiness adventure in Bulgaria, register today 🙌 https://www.f6s.com/entreprenedu-hackthebusinessbulgaria/apply</p> <p>Your #sustainable innovation could be the idea we are looking for!</p> <p>● ● ●</p>	<p>HTB BULGARIA registration 5 days</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7176184872384790528</p>
<p>🕒 3 DAYS 🕒 Step 1, register 🙌 https://www.f6s.com/entreprenedu-hackthebusinessbulgaria/apply Step 2, unlock the secrets to building a #winning team 🙌 https://entreprenedu.eu/how-to-build-a-winning-team-at-the-hackthebusiness-contest-strategies-for-success/ Step 3: #HackTheBusiness in Bulgaria with us 🚀</p> <p>● ● ●</p>	<p>HTB BULGARIA registration 3 days</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7176832262238306304</p>
<p>🕒 FINAL DAY 🕒 #HackTheBusiness adventure is just around the corner and the excitement level is rising! You have still a few more hours to register and join us 🙌 https://www.f6s.com/entreprenedu-hackthebusinessbulgaria/apply</p> <p>● ● ●</p>	<p>HTB BULGARIA registration LAST DAY</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:717952581732728832</p>
<p>Welcome to the first day of the #HackTheBusiness event in Bulgaria, a day full of exciting activities for our participants! 😎</p> <p>Their #HackTheBusiness experience started with meeting #ENTREPRENEDU team (EDU included) and learning about diverse #business tips and tricks from our experts. 🧠</p> <p>Moreover, they had time to meet each other and set the ground for their innovative and sustainable ideas! 🌱</p>	<p>HTB Bulgaria Day 1</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7178349277209907201</p>

<p>Our green-adventure continues tomorrow! #StayTuned</p> <p></p>		
<p>After 48h, they hacked the business in the heart of Bulgaria! 🤓 Well done teams - you showed creativity, sustainable way of thinking and professionalism! 🌟 Now, you will have a chance to participate in #ENTREPRENEDEU Mentoring and Coaching Programme where our experts will be guiding your entrepreneurial journey! 🙌</p> <p>CONGRAGULATIONS! 🎉🎊🎊🎊</p> <p>Besides #HackTheBusiness participants, a big thank you goes to all organisers, especially Cleantech Bulgaria, as well as our amazing mentors and inspiring speakers! Thank you all for your contribution to the final #HackTheBusiness competition - it was an incredible journey! 🌟</p> <p></p>	<p>HTB Bulgaria Day 2</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:718781381706076160</p>
<p>🎊 Meet #HackTheBusiness #Bulgaria winners 🎊</p> <p>👉👉👉 LOCAL.</p> <p>Congratulations team! 🙌 You hacked the business in Bulgaria and grabbed the opportunity to enter #ENTREPRENEDEU Mentoring and Coaching Programme & level-up your business idea into a real startup! 🤓</p> <p></p> <p>#ENTREPRENEDEU #HackTheBusiness #Bulgaria #Winners</p>	<p>HTB BULGARIA Meet the Winners</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7180570338211045376</p>
<p>🎊 Meet #HackTheBusiness #Bulgaria winners 🎊</p> <p>👉👉👉 Brick3D</p> <p>Congratulations team! 🙌 You hacked the business in Bulgaria and grabbed the opportunity to enter #ENTREPRENEDEU Mentoring and Coaching Programme & level-up your business idea into a real startup! 🤓</p>	<p>HTB BULGARIA Meet the Winners</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7180834889296945153</p>

<p>#ENTREPRENEDU #HackTheBusiness #Bulgaria #Winners</p>		
<p>#ENTREPRENEDU #HackTheBusiness #Bulgaria #Winners</p>	<p>HTB BULGARIA Meet the Winners SCHEDULED</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7181206336989188096</p>
<p>#ENTREPRENEDU #HackTheBusiness #Bulgaria #Winners</p>	<p>HTB BULGARIA Meet the Winners SCHEDULED</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7181568706097905664</p>
Green Team <p>Congratulations team! 🏆 You hacked the business in Bulgaria and grabbed the opportunity to enter #ENTREPRENEDU Mentoring and Coaching Programme & level-up your business idea into a real startup! 😎</p>	<p>HTB BULGARIA Meet the Winners SCHEDULED</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7181931097423802368</p>

 #ENTREPRENEDU #HackTheBusiness #Bulgaria #Winners		
<p>Once more, ENTREPRENEDU congratulates to all winning teams – you hacked the business in Bulgaria! 🤓 Learn more about the Bulgarian #HackTheBusiness adventure! 👉</p> <p>https://lnkd.in/ei6nNZU4</p>	HTB BULGARIA Blog Article	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7183814540508172288
<p>Closing this week with a recap of the #HackTheBusiness #Bulgaria hackathon! 🎉 It was a mixture of hard work, diligence and fun! 🤓👏</p> <p>👉 https://lnkd.in/eC4Njp_f</p> <p>As the curtains close on this transformative chapter, the legacy of #HackTheBusiness lingers, while ENTREPRENEDU journey towards enhancing entrepreneurial ecosystems for European education continues! ✨</p>	HTB BULGARIA Final Video	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7184540973228527618
<p>ENTREPRENEDU was presented by Fondazione E. Amaldi at the eighth edition of Spring of Innovation held on 4th and 5th of April in Turin! Every year, this event explore trends, addresses challenges and brings out opportunities in the world of innovation and technology transfer in Italy! 🙌</p> <p>This year's theme was “INNOVATION AND SUSTAINABILITY FOR SPACE”, a compelling journey where cutting-edge technology meets eco-sustainable solutions to redefine space exploration and industrial evolution. 🚀+🌱</p> <p>Our Project Coordinator, Fondazione E. Amaldi introduced hashtag#ENTREPRENEDU by showcasing our mission, our goals and future plans! ✨</p>	Spring of Innovation, Turin	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7185550825589501953
<p>Do you ❤️ hashtag#Fridays? 📧 ENTREPRENEDU hashtag#newsletter is out in the email-world and it's full with exciting news and a special hashtag#Friday surprise! 🎵</p>	NL #5	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:718

<p>Missed it? 😞 Subscribe and stay in the hashtag#ENTREPRENEDU knowledge loop 🧠 👉👉👉 http://eepurl.com/ilqOzv</p> <p>●●●</p>		6996429402374145
<p>🎉 We are happy to announce the kick-off of the hashtag#ENTREPRENEDU Mentoring & Coaching Programme - Cohort 3. 🚀 To learn more about this amazing Programme, read the article below 👁️👉 https://lnkd.in/ePKMijug</p> <p>●●●</p>	<p>Mentoring & Coaching Programme</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7188187033289334784
<p>#TuesdayTip: Subscribe and stay in the #ENTREPRENEDU knowledge loop 🧠👉 http://eepurl.com/ilqOzv</p> <p>●●●</p>	<p>NL Subscription</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7190983275878719488
<p>Today we celebrate #EuropeDay ✨ https://lnkd.in/eXZff2E6</p> <p>#ENTREPRENEDU is an EU-funded initiative with a mission to enhance entrepreneurial ecosystems for European education.</p> <p>●●●</p>	<p>Europe Day</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7194269661134245888
<p>Indeed, time flies by when you work hard & have fun! 😎</p> <p>#ENTREPRENEDU #HorizonEU #HackTheBusiness #Education #YoungEntrepreneurs #Startups #Innovation</p>	<p>Repost from FEA</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7197170869557706752
<p>#RecapTime Remember when we hacked the business in #Italy? 👉👤 https://lnkd.in/e9paWGBi</p> <p>●●●</p>	<p>HTB Recap #1</p>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7199043873694773249

<p>#ENTREPRENEDU #EUproject #HorizonEurope #HorizonEU</p>		
<p>#RecapTime We are e-travelling to #Greece to revisit all the great time we had in Athens with our #HackTheBusiness participants! </p> <p>#ENTREPRENEDU #EUproject #HorizonEurope #HorizonEU</p>	<p>HTB Recap #2</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7201909167995953153</p>
	<p>Repost from FEA</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7203318012672626690</p>
<p>#RecapTime In our minds, today we are in #Bulgaria hacking the business! </p> <p>#ENTREPRENEDU #EUproject #HorizonEurope #HorizonEU</p>	<p>HTB Recap #3</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7204811089992105985</p>
<p>ENTREPRENEDU #interviews are live! </p>	<p>Interviews: Fraunhofer IPK</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7206942085482975232</p>
<p>ENTREPRENEDU #Recommendations </p>	<p>Recommendati</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7206942085482975232</p>

<p>If you are not sure which #movie to watch during this #weekend, maybe this one will spark the interest of all of you, future #Founders 🌟</p> <p>Let us know what you think about the movie in the comments 🗨️</p> <p>📄 https://lnkd.in/dsQ8NzN</p> <p>●●●</p>	<p>ons</p>	<p>ed/update/urn:li:activity:7207343214649880577</p>
<p>ENTREPRENEDU #interviews are live! 🗣️</p> <p>Join us as we dive deep into conversations with #ENTREPRENEDU experts, uncovering invaluable insights about each of six Mentoring & Coaching Programme modules! 🌟</p> <p>We talked with Fabio Biscotti, Business Development Specialist of Fondazione E. Amaldi and a Mentor of “Your Idea Pitch: from Tech Feasibility to Product Development” module.</p> <p>Take a look of what Fabio had to say about the Programme and its benefits.</p> <p>👁️ https://lnkd.in/eV4m8UcT</p> <p>●●●</p>	<p>Interviews: FEA</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7209200916086829058</p>
<p>ENTREPRENEDU #Recommendations 💡</p> <p>Hey #Entrepreneurs, here's an idea of a great book you could read by the end of June! 📖 Has someone already had a pleasure? Let us know in the comments below! 🗨️</p> <p>●●●</p>	<p>Recommendations</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7209548910099378176</p>
<p>ENTREPRENEDU #interviews are live! 🗣️</p> <p>Join us as we dive deep into conversations with #ENTREPRENEDU experts, uncovering invaluable insights about each of six Mentoring & Coaching Programme modules! 🌟</p>	<p>Interviews: Luiss</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7212090551536365568</p>

<p>We interviewed Paola B., Lecturer on Innovation Management and Entrepreneurship at Luiss Guido Carli University and a Mentor of “Your Idea Pitch: from Tech Feasibility to Product Development” module.</p> <p>Take a look of what Paola had to say about the Programme and its benefits. https://lnkd.in/e92bRm8R</p>		
<p>ENTREPRENEDU #Recommendations 💡</p> <p>Have you watched the story of the #Facebook origin? Let us know what you think about the movie in the comments 🗣️</p> <p>	<p>Recommendations</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:72124461067716894722</p>
<p>ENTREPRENEDU #interviews are live! 🗣️</p> <p>Join us as we dive deep into conversations with #ENTREPRENEDU experts, uncovering invaluable insights about each of six Mentoring & Coaching Programme modules! ✨</p> <p>This time, we talked with Jacopo Piccagli, an #EU project manager at EBAN - European Business Angel Network and a Mentor of “Investment Pitch and Quantifying Your Funding Needs” module.</p> <p>Take a look of what Jacopo had to say about the Programme and its benefits. https://entreprenedu.eu/entreprenedu-mentoring-coaching-programme-insights-from-european-business-angel-network/</p> <p>#ENTREPRENEDU #EUproject #HorizonEurope #HorizonEU #Mentoring #Coaching #YoungEntrepreneurs</p>	<p>Interviews: EBAN</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7213813686233116673</p>

https://theinclusivestartupplaybook.buzzsprout.com/2314738/14675396-how-to-manage-trust	Recommendations	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7214923370675535873
<p>ENTREPRENEDU #interviews are live! 🗣️</p> <p>Join us as we dive deep into conversations with #ENTREPRENEDU experts, uncovering invaluable insights about each of six Mentoring & Coaching Programme modules! 🌟</p> <p>We very thrilled to talk with Orfeas Voutyras, Research #Engineer and Senior Advisor at Corallia and a Mentor of “Entrepreneurial Business Planning” module.</p> <p>Take a look of what Orfeas had to say about the Programme and its benefits.</p> <p>👁️ https://entreprenedu.eu/entreprenedu-mentoring-coaching.../</p> <p>🟦🟡🟠</p>	Interviews: Corallia	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:721446886914297856
<p>ENTREPRENEDU #interviews are live! 🗣️</p> <p>Join us as we dive deep into conversations with #ENTREPRENEDU experts, uncovering invaluable insights about each of six Mentoring & Coaching Programme modules! 🌟</p> <p>Last, but not least, we talked with Ina Todorova, Project Coordinator at Cleantech Bulgaria and a Mentor of “Access to Finance and Related Funding” module.</p> <p>Take a look of what Ina had to say about the Programme and its benefits.</p> <p>👁️ https://entreprenedu.eu/entreprenedu-mentoring-coaching-programme-insights-from-cleantech-bulgaria/</p> <p>🟦🟡🟠</p>	Interviews: CleanTech	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7219337135986720769
ENTREPRENEDU #newsletter is out in the email-world 📧 Inside, you will find out what is coming next, right after the summer break! 🌟	Newsletter #6	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7219337135986720769

<p>Curious? Subscribe and stay in the #ENTREPRENEDEU knowledge loop 🧠</p> <p>👉👉👉 http://eepurl.com/ilqOzv</p> <p>🟡🟠🔴</p>		<p>ed/update/urn:li:activity:7219611944205328385</p>
<p>🚀 We might see you at European Angel Investment Summit, in Brussels on 15th - 16th October 👉 https://lnkd.in/d/fRpwmv</p> <p>Organised by our teammates from EBAN - European Business Angel Network - the #EAIS24 conference is where connections flourish, expert knowledge is shared, and a unique platform is offered to network with investors and entrepreneurs from all over Europe and beyond. 🙌</p> <p>Apply before September 15th to make your startup the next big success story!</p> <p>🟡🟠🔴</p> <p>#ENTREPRENEDEU #HorizonEurope #InnovationEcosystem #EUProject</p>	<p>EBAN event promotion</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7221873857199042560</p>
<p>ENTREPRENEDEU #Recommendations 💡</p> <p>This #summer, find the answer to why #startups fail by reading this great book! 📖</p> <p>🟡🟠🔴</p> <p>#ENTREPRENEDEU #EUproject #HorizonEurope #HorizonEU</p>	<p>Recommendations</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/posts/entrepreneu_recommendations-summer-startups-activity-7225088056062554112-9pSl?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop</p>
<p>ENTREPRENEDEU #Recommendations 💡</p> <p>Find some #inspiration for that #idea crusing in your head!</p> <p>🌟 https://www.business.com/articles/10-inspiring-entrepreneurs-40/ 💡</p>	<p>Recommendations</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7226859617920700416</p>

<p>#ENTREPRENEDU #EUproject #HorizonEurope #HorizonEU</p>		
<p>ENTREPRENEDU #Recommendations 💡</p> <p>Have you already had a time to watch the story of the meteoric rise and catastrophic demise of the world's first smartphone? 📱 If not, we recommend it! ✨</p> <p>🎬 https://www.imdb.com/title/tt21867434/?ref_=tt_sims_tt_i_2</p> <p>#ENTREPRENEDU #EUproject #HorizonEurope #HorizonEU</p>	Recommendations	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7229396374423830528
<p>ENTREPRENEDU #Recommendations 💡</p> <p>Resolve all of your #founder dilemmas with this book!</p> <p>#ENTREPRENEDU #EUproject #HorizonEurope #HorizonEU</p>	Recommendations	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7231933109842169856
<p>ENTREPRENEDU #Recommendations 💡</p> <p>The story about not giving up! 🙌</p> <p>🎬 https://www.imdb.com/title/tt0454921/</p> <p>#ENTREPRENEDU #EUproject #HorizonEurope #HorizonEU</p>	Recommendations	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7234469809160097792

<p>ENTREPRENEDU #Recommendations 💡</p> <p>This September, motivation is the key to keep rocking! 🚀 https://www.business.com/articles/how-to-stay-motivated-to-start-a-business/</p> <p>🟦🟧🟥</p> <p>#ENTREPRENEDU #EUproject #HorizonEurope #HorizonEU</p>	<p>Recommendations</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7237006521492992000</p>
<p>ENTREPRENEDU #Recommendations 💡</p> <p>If you don't ask - you will never know! 🤔</p> <p>🟦🟧🟥</p> <p>#ENTREPRENEDU #EUproject #HorizonEurope #HorizonEU</p>	<p>Recommendations</p>	<p>Scheduled</p>
<p>Do you know #EDU? 🤔</p> <p>Get to know hashtag#EDU and hashtag#ENTREPRENEDU by watching the video below! 📺</p> <p>https://lnkd.in/eiwusAym</p> <p>In short, the concept of ENTREPRENEDU is focused on closing the innovation and educational gap between different regions of the #EU, causing unbalanced business activity and fewer job opportunities in less developed entrepreneurial ecosystems.</p> <p>🟦🟧🟥</p> <p>#ENTREPRENEDU #EUproject #HorizonEurope #HorizonEU</p>	<p>Reminder</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7242113300551864320</p>
<p>The end always marks <small>NEW</small> beginnings.</p> <p>Mentoring & Coaching Programme led by ENTREPRENEDU experts had a mission to address the challenges faced by young #entrepreneurs who are in</p>	<p>M&C Programme</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:724</p>

<p>need of a support in their professional journey while creating potentially groundbreaking #businesses. 🌸</p> <p>As the Programme has officially ended, we spoke with some of our participants to learn their feedback on the hashtag#ENTREPRENEDU journey! ✨</p> <p>🗣️ Merilin Petrova, Co-Founder at Paw Paw 🇬🇷</p> <p>P.S. Well done, we are always cheering for you! 🥳</p> <p>Read more about the Programme and its impact in our latest blog post 📌 https://lnkd.in/eqVYeaxr</p> <p>🟦🟡🟠</p>	<p>End</p>	<p>4646337244200960</p>
<p>The Mentoring & Coaching Programme, led by experts from #ENTREPRENEDU, aimed to support young #entrepreneurs navigating the challenges of building potentially groundbreaking #businesses. 🌸 Now that the Programme has concluded, we caught up with some participants to hear their reflections on the #ENTREPRENEDU journey! ✨</p> <p>🗣️ Nikoleta Petkova, Founder at Edna Bulgarka 🇧🇬</p> <p>P.S. Congratulations - we're always rooting for you! 🥳 Learn more about the Programme and its impact in our latest blog post 📌 https://lnkd.in/eqVYeaxr</p> <p>🟦🟡🟠</p>	<p>M&C Programme End</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7247151019984400384</p>
<p>After 3 #HackTheBusiness events and 3 cohorts of young #entrepreneurs from #Italy #Greece and #Bulgaria joining the #ENTREPRENEDU journey - it is time to celebrate the successful ending of the ENTREPRENEDU Mentoring & Coaching Programme! ✨</p> <p>Read more in our newest #PressArticle 📌 🗣️ https://lnkd.in/ekeZdqV2</p> <p>🟦🟡🟠</p>	<p>M&C Programme End Press Release</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7250428485930749952</p>

<p>Hey, hey, we are traveling to Bulgaria! ✈️ 🗨️ We'll be exhibiting at #WEBIT2024 event on October 23-24 in Sofia, where we are going to promote #ENTREPRENEDU future activities!</p> <p>Are we gonna see you there? 🙄</p> <p>🟡🟢🔴</p>	<p>Event dissemination: Webit</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7251922267004178432</p>
<p>See you next week in #Bulgaria! 🙌</p>	<p>Event dissemination: Webit</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7252215453702307841</p>
<p>ENTREPRENEDU #newsletter is out in the email-world ✉️ Curious what is inside? Subscribe and stay in the #ENTREPRENEDU knowledge loop 🧠👉 http://eepurl.com/ilqOzv</p> <p>🟡🟢🔴</p>	<p>NL #7</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7252678694534623233</p>
<p>#ENTREPRENEDU is at the hashtag#WEBIT2024 / hashtag#FutureForum2024 event at F6S Innovation booth on 6th floor at National Palace of Culture in Sofia, Bulgaria! 🙌 We are talking to young entrepreneurs about how we are enhancing entrepreneurial education ecosystem across European Union! 😊</p> <p>🟡🟢🔴</p>	<p>Webit</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7255212491880689664</p>
<p>Our partner F6S Innovation, was at hashtag#Webit2024 / hashtag#FutureForum2024 event in National Palace of Culture in Sofia, Bulgaria during 23d and 24th of October, 2024! 🙌</p> <p>#ENTREPRENEDU team is happy to support future entrepreneurs and enhancing their ways towards owning successful startups!</p> <p>🟡🟢🔴</p>	<p>Webit</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7255238226137825280</p>
<p>The International Astronautical Congress (IAC) is an annual global event in the field of space exploration and technology, attracting over 6,000 participants. It serves as a platform for professionals, scientists, engineers, and enthusiasts to exchange knowledge, showcase advancements, and discuss space-related topics. 🤖</p> <p>ENTREPRENEDU was presented by our Project Manager Valerio Roscani, PhD from Fondazione E. Amaldi in front of an audience of students,</p>	<p>International Astronautical Congress (IAC)</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7257315353905565696</p>

<p>communication experts, professors and managers of space-themed education programmes. The presentation helped to make the project known in an international context in terms of networking and visibility. 🚀</p> <p>●●●</p>		
<p>It's not a secret that hashtag#ENTREPRENEDU project, together with an amazing team of different hashtag#EU stakeholders and with a help of hashtag#EDU is working hard to enhance and streamline entrepreneurial education across European Union. 😊</p> <p>With that aim in our minds, we have organised three hashtag#HackTheBusiness events - in Italy, Greece and Bulgaria, and gathered young entrepreneurs willing to learn more, share feedback and upgrade their professional knowledge by participating in the Mentoring & Coaching Programme which has successfully ended! ✨</p> <p>Now, it's time for a new chapter in the hashtag#ENTREPRENEDU journey, chapter named ENTREPRENEDU Venture Building Programme. This Programme objective is to create a scalable and replicable educational model, which addresses regional disparities in innovation across Europe.</p> <p>Learn more in our newest hashtag#blog article: https://lnkd.in/eS45BEqn</p>	<p>VBP</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7259852022902833153</p>
<p>#ENTREPRENEDU Venture Building Programme is currently in the focus of the hashtag#ENTREPRENEDU project journey! This Programme objective is to create a hashtag#scalable and replicable hashtag#educational model, which addresses regional disparities in innovation across hashtag#EU. 🙌</p> <p>We sat down with Jacopo Piccagli, EU Project Manager at hashtag#EBAN and a Venture Building Programme main organiser, to learn more about the main objectives of the Programme and the journey behind transformation of the entrepreneurial education. 📌</p> <p>Learn more: https://lnkd.in/eS45BEqn</p> <p>Thank you Jacopo Piccagli for your valuable insights!</p>	<p>VBP</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7262431202593193985</p>
<p>ENTREPRENEDU is creating a hashtag#scalable and replicable hashtag#educational model, which addresses regional disparities in innovation with an aim to enhance education for young & wannabe hashtag#entrepreneurs across hashtag#EU 🙌</p>	<p>VBP</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:726</p>

<p>Learn more about hashtag#ENTREPRENEDU Venture Building Programme! </p> <p>https://lnkd.in/eS45BEqn</p>		<p>5294680890781696</p>
<p>We talked with Jacopo Piccagli, EU Project Manager at EBAN - European Business Angel Network and a Venture Building Programme organiser, to learn more about the main objectives of the Programme and the journey behind. 📌 Thank you Jacopo Piccagli for your time and insights! 🙌</p> <p>Learn more: https://lnkd.in/eS45BEqn</p>	<p>VBP</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7267485918482071554</p>
<p>We're thrilled to share that our partner, Katrin Singer-Coudoux from Fraunhofer Institute for Production Systems and Design Technology IPK recently presented ENTREPRENEDU to two groups of bright young students! 🧠 Her talks were part of the Talent Take-Off initiative of Femtec Network and Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft. 🍷</p> <p>Special thanks to Ruth Asan for giving us the opportunity to inspire the next wave of entrepreneurial talent during this initiative! ✨</p> <p>Learn more about how hashtag#ENTREPRENEDU is enhancing entrepreneurial education of young wannabe founders across hashtag#EU! </p>	<p>Fraunhofer workshop</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7270011948497281024</p>
<p>Remember EDU? EDU is a #student, wannabe #entrepreneur who joined the ENTREPRENEDU journey and hacked the business with the help of ENTREPRENEDU mentors! Now, EDU is helping our team to understand what should be improved in the European educational system, to support young entrepreneurs and help them achieving their dreams.</p> <p>With EDU's help, we are creating a Venture Building Programme, a #scalable and replicable #educational model, which addresses regional disparities in innovation across #EU. 🙌</p> <p></p> <p>#ENTREPRENEDU #HorizonEurope #InnovationEcosystem #EUProject #Education #Students #Youth #Entrepreneurs #University</p>	<p>ENTREPRENEDU Video</p>	

<p>We are happy to showcase a sneak peak to a final session of the Venture Building Programme in Bulgaria!</p> <p>Learn more about this engaging initiative! https://entreprenedu.eu/</p> <p>●●●</p>	<p>Cleantech Recording</p>	
<p>This holiday season, take some time to rest, be with loved ones and recharge! ❤️</p> <p>Happy holidays from the ENTREPRENEDU team! ❄️</p>	<p>EDU Holidays</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7277623340989612032</p>
<p>As we wrap up this year, we want to take a moment to celebrate you – the dreamers, the doers, and the ones who are ready to make things happen. ✨</p> <p>We wish you a jolly and successful #2025! 🍷</p>	<p>EDU Holidays</p>	<p>Scheduled</p>
<p>📧 ✨ New year, new updates! Jump into the #ENTREPRENEDU knowledge pool - join others and subscribe now! ☀️ http://eepurl.com/ilqOzv</p> <p>●●●</p>	<p>NEWSLETTER SUBSCRIPTION</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7282682508616318975</p>
<p>#2025 update: #ENTREPRENEDU marks 2 years of enhancing entrepreneurial ecosystems for European education! 🎂 #HappyBirthday to us! 🍰</p> <p>#ENTREPRENEDU team will keep working on erasing the educational imbalances in Europe and supporting youth on their entrepreneurial journey! ☀️</p> <p>P.S. Are you new here? Welcome! Learn what we do in 30s directly from our Project Coordinator! ✂️ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=cYu8ZESSF3c</p>	<p>2 years of ENTREPRENEDU</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7285219222119481345</p>
<p>ENTREPRENEDU academic partners are currently presenting the Venture Building Programme directly to students interested in entrepreneurship. For example, this week, Achilles Barlas, Professor at the University of Thessaly from Greece, gave a lecture to the 97 students, from which 38 already</p>	<p>VBP: UTH</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/posts/entreprenedu_entrepre</p>

<p>have a business idea - remarkable, right? 💡</p>		<p>nedu-entrepreneu-horizon-europe-activity-7285944000258179072-8MWk?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop</p>
<p>ENTREPRENEDU #newsletter is out in the email-world! ✉️ Missed it? 😊 Here's a sneak peak! 👁️ 🖱️ https://mailchi.mp/3559e49c61a4/thelastchapter</p>	<p>NL #8</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/posts/entrepreneu_newsletter-entrepreneu-horizoneu-activity-7287755984549101568-3blp?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop</p>